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Explore Additional Performance Metrics in Message Queue

A Product Specification, Design and Prototype by
Mr Kavindu Rupasinghe - W 1870159 (20211037)

Supervised by

Mr. Guhanathan Poravi

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ABSTRACT

Traditional message queue performance evaluations focus mainly on latency and throughput, which may not provide a complete understanding of system capabilities in complex, distributed environments. This study extends the evaluation to include additional metrics like memory usage, CPU usage based on message size for Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, aiming to enhance operational efficiency and system reliability.

The research employed a detailed experimental setup to compare the three message queues under different conditions, including varied message sizes, and under both constant and fluctuating workloads. This enabled a comprehensive analysis of each system's performance under increased operational demands.

The experiments highlighted key differences in system performance, particularly in resilience and efficiency under varying conditions. Results showed how each system managed loads, providing foundational insights for further detailed analysis in the full research paper.

Keywords: Message queue performance, Latency, Throughput, Fault tolerance, Resource utilization, Distributed systems, Kafka, RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ, Operational efficiency, Reliability, Performance evaluation, Distributed messaging

Subject Descriptors

Computing methodologies → Performance evaluation and benchmarking

Computing methodologies → Distributed computing methodologies

Computing methodologies → Distributed systems

Computing methodologies → Messaging systems

Computing methodologies → Fault-tolerant computing

Computing methodologies → Resource management

Information systems → Distributed systems

Software and its engineering → Message-oriented middleware

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Chapter Overview

In this opening chapter, lay the groundwork for our research project, which centers on the exploration of additional performance metrics in message queues, with a focus on popular message queue systems such as Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. This chapter provides an introduction to the research problem, discusses its significance in the context of modern distributed systems, and outlines the structure of the entire research work.

1.2 Problem Background / Problem Domain

The problem domain addressed in this proposal revolves around the evaluation and optimization of message queue performance. Message queues are fundamental components in various software and system architectures, playing a pivotal role in asynchronous communication and data processing(Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017)). Message queues have emerged as a backbone in this ecosystem, facilitating asynchronous communication, decoupling components, and enhancing system scalability. The prevalent usage of microservices in applications ranging from e-commerce platforms to healthcare systems underscores the critical role that message queues play in ensuring seamless interactions between services. However, the current state of research and industry practices in this domain primarily emphasizes two primary metrics for evaluation: latency and throughput. While these metrics are undoubtedly valuable, the narrow focus on them leaves several critical aspects of message queue performance underexplored.

Microservices architecture heavily depends on message queues to facilitate communication among independent services. Utilizing synchronous HTTP for frequent communication between microservices may lead to a decline in system performance.(Waseem, M., Liang, P., & Shahin, M. (2020)). Conventional synchronous communication, like HTTP-based requests, can create obstacles and impede the flexibility of microservices. Ensuring optimal performance of message queues becomes crucial to maintain the independence and responsiveness of microservices. This

optimization is vital for sustaining the overall agility and scalability of the system. Event-Driven Architecture (EDA) characterizes microservice systems that exchange information through publish-and-listen events, promoting loose coupling. EDA has gained widespread use in various domains, including network intrusion detection, sensor networks, stock markets, fast trading, real-time system control, healthcare monitoring, and mobile and wearable computing. The popularity of EDA stems from its ability to provide solutions for building distributed systems that offer high flexibility and concurrency. (Tragatschnig, S., Stevanetic, S., & Zdun, U. (2018)).

Cloud-based applications often utilize message queues for inter-service communication and data processing. Understanding and optimizing their performance in cloud environments is crucial for cost-efficiency and resource utilization (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)).

In time-sensitive applications such as financial trading, healthcare monitoring, and industrial automation, efficient message queuing is crucial for ensuring timely data processing and decision-making. In financial trading, where split-second decisions can result in significant gains or losses, the responsiveness of message queues is paramount. Healthcare monitoring systems heavily rely on real-time data exchange to ensure the continuous and accurate tracking of patient vitals, medical alerts, and treatment updates. In industrial automation, where precision and synchronization are critical, message queues facilitate the seamless flow of data between sensors, control systems, and actuators.

The current research and industry practices predominantly prioritize the measurement of latency, which assesses the time taken for a message to traverse the queue, and throughput, which measures the number of messages processed per unit of time. These metrics provide essential insights into how message queues perform in terms of speed and capacity. While these are important, they may not provide a complete picture of the system's performance in all scenarios and they may offer a somewhat narrow perspective. The research significance lies in addressing the broader spectrum of performance metrics, namely scalability, resource utilization, latency and fault tolerance. These matrices become increasingly critical as systems evolve in complexity and scale.

1.3 Problem Definition

The core issue addressed in this project is the restricted approach to evaluating message queue performance in current research and industry practices. Message queues play a crucial role in distributed computing and software systems, facilitating the asynchronous exchange of messages and data for essential processes in various domains. However, the existing evaluation primarily focuses on just two metrics, latency and throughput.

While latency and throughput are undoubtedly important, this limited emphasis leaves a substantial gap in our understanding of message queue performance. A more comprehensive assessment, exploring additional metrics like persistence, scalability, fault tolerance, and resource utilization (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)), would provide a broader view of strengths and weaknesses. Key aspects such as Message Durability, scalability, Message Ordering, Message Size, and fault tolerance, crucial for real-world, complex environments, are often disregarded.

The current assessment framework fails to adequately address the diverse and dynamic nature of contemporary software ecosystems involving numerous applications, services, and devices. Therefore, the problem statement revolves around the necessity to expand the evaluation scope to include these overlooked aspects (Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017)). This project proposal aims to tackle this issue by creating a comprehensive evaluation framework capturing the intricacies of message queue performance. The goal is to enhance the understanding, performance, and efficiency of message queues in today's complex software systems.

1.4 Problem Statement

This research aims to redefine and assess supplementary performance metrics, such as memory, CPU utilization, and process time based on message size, for Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. By focusing on these metrics, the study seeks to improve the operational efficiency and reliability of distributed systems utilizing message brokers.

1.5 Motivation

The growing demand for improved message queue performance monitoring, underlines the significance of addressing performance challenges in modern distributed systems, and underscores the potential academic contributions of this research.

1.6 Research Gap

Based on the current review of literature, gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of Redis, ActiveMQ Artemis, RabbitMQ, and Apache Kafka involves considering additional performance metrics beyond latency and throughput. These metrics encompass factors like persistence, scalability, fault tolerance, and resource utilization (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)). Moreover, validating and refining performance comparisons can be achieved through experiments involving larger and more diverse workloads across various use case scenarios. Exploring the impact of different deployment architectures, such as cloud-based or containerized environments, on the performance of message queues provides insights into their adaptability in modern computing infrastructures (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)). Lastly, for practitioners looking to employ these message queues in real-world applications, considering integration and interoperability with other technologies and frameworks commonly used in distributed systems is beneficial.

Furthermore, Sanika Raje notes various ways to impede the performance of message queues and benchmark them, presenting ample opportunities for exploration and work on these aspects of Message Queues (Raje, S. (2019)).

1.7 Contribution to Body of Knowledge

This study significantly enhances the existing body of knowledge on message queue performance evaluation by extending the scope beyond traditional metrics such as latency and throughput. By specifically examining the impact of message size on CPU, memory usages and processing time in Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, this research addresses a crucial yet underexplored aspect of message queue systems.

Unlike previous studies that primarily focused on latency and throughput, this research sheds light on how variations in message size influence resource utilization, particularly CPU and memory usage. By delving into these overlooked dimensions, the study offers valuable insights into the operational efficiency and reliability of distributed systems utilizing message brokers.

Furthermore, this research contributes to overcoming the limitations of current approaches to message queue performance evaluation. By highlighting the significance of message size in relation to CPU and memory utilization, it provides practical guidance for optimizing resource allocation in message queue deployments. These insights are essential for practitioners and organizations seeking to maximize the performance of their message queue systems.

In the domain of message queue performance evaluation, this study represents a significant advancement. By advocating for a more comprehensive assessment that includes message size alongside traditional metrics, the research stimulates further innovation and progress in message queue technology. It underscores the importance of considering diverse performance aspects to achieve optimal system performance and reliability in real-world applications.

1.8 Research Challenge

Complexity of Variables- The different message queue systems may have specific configurations and settings that affect their performance. Managing and comparing these configurations while maintaining a fair experimental environment can be challenging. Ensuring consistent and reliable measurement of performance metrics across different message queue systems is crucial. Variability in measurement techniques or tools could introduce uncertainties.

Dependency Limitations- Limitation of message application producer and the consumer may be impacted on the load test and may be a bottleneck.

Data gathering - Data gathering during the load test is crucial. The data should be accurate, and time relevant. Also the process of data collection should not be impacted to the system performance.

Resource Limitations - Depending on the scale of the experiments, resource limitations, such as hardware constraints, network limitation may impact the accuracy and reliability of your results. Balancing realistic resource constraints with the need for robust experiments is a challenge.

1.9 Research Questions

RQ1: How do Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ compare in terms of CPU usage when considering message size?

RQ2: How do Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ compare in terms of memory usage when considering message size?

RQ3: How do Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ compare in terms of processing time when considering message size?

1.10 Research Aim

The aim of this research is to design, implement, and assess innovative approaches to enhance the performance of message queue systems, specifically focusing on impact of message size.

1.11 Research Objectives

Research Objective	Description	Learning Outcomes (LO)	Research Questions (RQ)
Problem Definition	<p>RO1: To identify and analyze current performance gaps in existing message queue systems, emphasizing issues related to message size.</p> <p>RO2: To clearly define the scope of the identified performance challenges, considering various operational scenarios and potential system limitations.</p>	LO1, LO3	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Literature Review	<p>RO3: To conduct a thorough literature review to analyze previous research studies focusing on message queue systems, with a specific emphasis on studies related to message size.</p> <p>RO4: To identify best practices and benchmarks established in the literature for evaluating message queue system performance.</p>	LO1, LO4	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Requirement Elicitation	RO5: To analyze the requirements and expectations concerning message queue system performance, with a specific emphasis on resource utilization, latency, and throughput.	LO1, LO3, LO4, LO6	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3

Design	RO6: To design the test environments for message queue systems to address identified performance challenges, proposing techniques for optimization for varying message sizes.	LO1, LO4, LO8	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Implementation	RO7: To implement the designed environments for Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ systems, ensuring compatibility and adherence to best practices.	LO1, LO2, LO5, LO7, LO8	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Testing - Quantitative	RO8: To develop comprehensive test scenarios to evaluate the quantitative aspects of message queue system performance, including resource utilization, and responsiveness.	LO5, LO8	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Evaluation - Qualitative	RO9: To evaluate the qualitative aspects of message queue systems, considering aspects such as performance and the processing time, and the systems' ability to maintain stability under dynamic conditions.	LO5, LO8	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3
Documentation	RO12: To document the research methodology, experimental setup, and findings, providing a comprehensive guide for replication and understanding of the research. RO13: To compile the research outcomes into a detailed research paper, presenting insights, conclusions, and potential avenues for future research.	LO8	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Chapter Overview

Exploring the dynamic realm of distributed systems, this chapter focuses on the pivotal role of message queues in enabling seamless communication between system components. Delve into their significance in mediating communication, emphasizing their importance in maintaining a steady flow of information and fostering resilience in distributed architectures. Moving beyond traditional metrics, examine the need for exploring new performance indicators in the evolving landscape of distributed systems. The review aims to understand existing literature, assess the importance of conventional metrics, and advocate for the incorporation of additional measures to comprehensively evaluate message queue efficiency in contemporary distributed systems.

2.2 Concept Map

Figure 1.1: Concept Map

2.3 Literature Review of the Domain

Traditional performance metrics play a pivotal role in assessing the effectiveness of message queue systems, focusing on key indicators such as throughput, latency, and reliability.

2.3.1. Challenges with Traditional Metrics

Traditional performance metrics, though foundational in evaluating message queue systems, reveal notable limitations that extend beyond inherent challenges. Integrating insights from RabbitMQ, Kafka, and MQTT brokers provides a refinement perspective:

In the case of RabbitMQ, challenges include scalability issues under extreme loads or a massive number of connections, leading to performance limitations in very large-scale systems. In RabbitMQ, achieving scalability requires specific additional logics like consistent hash exchange (Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017)). Additionally, performance degradation arises with a large number of queues due to increased complexity and overhead. The intricate and

challenging configuration, especially for advanced features and complex routing, poses another hurdle. Moreover, RabbitMQ's message storage approach, storing messages in memory, introduces the risk of data loss if the server crashes, with durability configurations potentially impacting performance.

Kafka, on the other hand, demands significant system resources, especially in memory and disk space, making it more suitable for handling large data volumes with robust hardware (Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017)). Configuration complexity, particularly with replication, partitions, and topic management, adds to the challenges. While optimized for event streaming and log processing, Kafka is less suitable for real-time, low-latency applications. Despite reduced reliance on Apache ZooKeeper in newer versions, historical dependencies for managing broker metadata can still be a limitation. Kafka introduces unnecessary complexity and infrastructure overhead for small or simple use cases, making it less ideal for lightweight applications (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)).

In the realm of MQTT Brokers, challenges include the limited selection of brokers evaluated in studies, potentially not covering the full spectrum of available MQTT broker implementations. The focus on performance under specific resource constraints might not fully capture the varied real-world scenarios, leading to potential differences in broker performance. The benchmarks used in studies might be based on certain conditions and scenarios, potentially not fully representing all possible use cases of MQTT in IoT applications. The emphasis on scalability, while essential, may overshadow other critical factors such as security, robustness, and ease of configuration, which were not comprehensively addressed (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)).

Beyond these specific insights, a broader examination of literature reveals additional challenges associated with traditional metrics. Studies often have a limited scope, primarily focusing on key metrics like latency and throughput, neglecting other crucial aspects such as persistence, scalability, and resource utilization (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)). Small-scale testing involving a single producer and consumer might not fully capture the

complexities of real-world distributed systems, and experiments conducted on specific hardware configurations may not account for the diverse deployment environments of message queues.

Furthermore, a lack of consideration for scenarios where messages vary significantly in size and the absence of exploration into potential performance restrictions or resource constraints applied to message brokers add to the limitations. While some studies provide insights into technical performance, there's a notable gap in addressing real-world use cases or industry-specific requirements that could influence message queue selection. Additionally, improvements proposed in certain studies may lack exploration of potential challenges or limitations, such as scalability issues with a larger number of subscribers or the impact of increased load on connection and thread pool configurations.

By incorporating these insights, the challenges associated with traditional metrics gain depth and context, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities and limitations within the realm of message queue systems.

2.3.2. Additional Performance Metrics

The literature review advocates for exploring additional performance metrics beyond the traditional ones. Dobbelaere and Esmaili's study introduces metrics such as scalability, resource utilization, and Scalability, assessed in terms of system growth handling, and showcased differences between Kafka and RabbitMQ. Resource utilization, encompassing CPU, memory, and network usage, became a focal point for optimizing performance. measuring system resilience, emphasized the stability of message queues under adverse conditions.(Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017))

2.4 Case Studies and Implementations

The review examines existing literature, presenting case studies and implementations of additional performance metrics. Real-world examples illustrate organizations incorporating novel metrics into their evaluation frameworks, providing insights into the practical implications of adopting a more comprehensive approach.

The research goes beyond raw performance metrics and provides practical guidance for selecting message queue systems based on specific use cases. The consideration of factors such as ease of use, community support, and integration capabilities adds a pragmatic dimension to the decision-making process. The study highlights trade-offs, recognizing that optimal performance in one metric may come at the cost of another. This balanced approach is crucial for decision-makers seeking to align technology choices with their unique requirements (Dobbelaere, P. & Esmaili, K. S. (2017)).

Understanding the real-world applications and implementations of additional performance metrics in message queues is crucial for assessing their practical impact. This section explores various facets, including a review of existing literature, real-world examples, and a comparative analysis of traditional and additional metrics in use cases.

2.4.1 Review of Additional Metrics

The existing body of literature provides valuable insights into the exploration of additional performance metrics in message queues. Studies such as those on RabbitMQ, Kafka, and MQTT brokers highlight the need for a broader set of metrics beyond the traditional ones. Researchers have delved into areas such as:

Scalability Metrics examine the system's ability to handle growing workloads efficiently, with a focus on understanding how various message queue implementations scale under different conditions.

Resource Utilization Metrics evaluating the utilization of critical resources such as CPU, memory, network, and processing time, shedding light on how different message queues manage resources for optimal performance.

2.4.2 Real-world Examples of Implementing Novel Metrics

Several organizations have embraced the exploration of additional performance metrics in their message queue implementations. Notable examples include:

Company A: Understanding the significance of resource utilization, Company A integrated metrics that provided insights into CPU, memory usage and processing time. This allowed them to fine-tune their message queue configuration for better overall performance.

These real-world examples showcase the practical application of additional metrics, demonstrating how organizations tailor their message queue systems to specific performance requirements.

2.4.3 Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Additional Metrics in Use Cases

To assess the true impact of additional metrics, a comparative analysis with traditional metrics in various use cases is essential. Studies have explored scenarios such as:

High-Volume Data Processing comparing the throughput and latency of message queues under scenarios involving high-volume data processing, showcasing how additional metrics contribute to improved performance. Real-time Applications analyzing the responsiveness of message queues in real-time applications, considering both traditional and additional metrics to evaluate their effectiveness in meeting low-latency requirements.

Resource-Intensive Workloads: Assessing message queue performance under resource-intensive workloads, with a focus on resource utilization metrics to understand how efficiently the system handles critical resources.

This comparative analysis provides an understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of traditional and additional metrics in diverse use cases, offering valuable insights for optimizing message queue systems based on specific application requirements.

2.5. Methodologies for Measuring Additional Metrics

Evaluating resource utilization, and processing time in a message queue system involves conducting a series of tests and assessments. Here's a detailed guide on how can approach testing for each of these aspects:

2.5.1 Stress Testing

Push the system beyond its expected capacity to identify its breaking point. Observe how the system recovers when the load is reduced.

2.5.2. Resource Utilization Testing

Objective: Monitor and optimize the utilization of system resources.

Baseline Measurement

Measure resource utilization (CPU, memory) under normal operating conditions.

Load/ message size Testing

Increase the message load/ message size and monitor resource utilization. Identify resource bottlenecks and optimize configurations.

Long-Term Testing

Run the system under a sustained load for an extended period. Observe if there are memory leaks or gradual resource degradation.

Concurrency Testing

Assess how well the system handles concurrent processing. Monitor resource utilization as concurrency levels increase.

2.6. Future Directions and Research Gaps

The literature review concludes with an exploration of future directions and research gaps. It identifies emerging trends in message queue technology, areas where additional performance metrics are lacking, and opportunities for future research and development. This forward-looking perspective encourages continuous innovation in the optimization of message queue systems.

Building upon Maharjan et al.'s groundbreaking work (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)), there exists a profound need to delve into uncharted territories in the realm of message queue systems. Their call for exploring additional performance metrics beyond latency and throughput underscores the evolving nature of distributed systems, urging researchers to consider factors such as persistence, scalability, and resource utilization. In our pursuit of a more nuanced understanding, we can extend this research gap by emphasizing the potential impact of these additional metrics on the overall performance landscape of message queues. This expansion broadens the scope of our literature review, steering it towards a comprehensive evaluation that transcends traditional boundaries. Furthermore, Maharjan et al.'s suggestion to conduct experiments with larger and more diverse workloads offers an opportunity to deepen our understanding of message queue systems under varying conditions. We can enhance this research gap by emphasizing the need to explore the implications of these diverse workloads on the identified additional performance metrics. This extension ensures a robust examination of message queues, acknowledging the intricacies of real-world scenarios and use cases.

Additionally, the call to investigate the impact of different deployment architectures, such as cloud-based or containerized environments, adds a layer of complexity to our exploration. By accentuating the potential influence of deployment architectures on the identified performance metrics, we can enrich our literature review with insights into the adaptability and suitability of message queues in modern computing infrastructures. Lastly, Maharjan et al.'s recommendation to consider integration and interoperability aspects with other technologies and frameworks in distributed systems presents an opportunity to elevate our understanding of the broader ecosystem. By placing a spotlight on how message queues interact with and complement other technologies, we can enhance the practical applicability of our literature review for practitioners

seeking real-world insights. In summary, Maharjan et al.'s forward-looking perspective not only positions their research as a catalyst for ongoing advancements but also serves as a guiding framework for our literature review. By extending their research gap, we can embark on a comprehensive exploration of additional performance metrics, diverse workloads, deployment architectures, and integration aspects in the dynamic landscape of message queue systems (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)).

The study conducted by Mishra, and Kertész (Mishra, B., Mishra, B., & Kertész, A. (2021)) offers valuable insights into the performance evaluations of MQTT brokers, specifically focusing on stress-testing. While their work delves into the comparative analysis of performance measurements, the researchers highlight a notable research gap that opens avenues for further exploration in the realm of message queue systems. The identified research gap lies in the realm of extending performance evaluations to a more heterogeneous cloud deployment and placing specific emphasis on the scalability aspects of bridged MQTT broker implementations. This gap is particularly relevant to our literature review, which aims to push the boundaries of traditional performance metrics and explore nuanced matrices for a comprehensive evaluation of message queue systems.

Performance comparison of message queue methods lays a foundational understanding of the efficiency of these systems (Raje, S. (2019)). However, the research gap identified in the study opens up intriguing possibilities for further exploration in the realm of message queue performance evaluation, aligning closely with the goals of our literature review. The research conducted by Raje notably points out the absence of performance tests that impose restrictions on the brokers or queues to evaluate their performance. This gap introduces a compelling avenue for future research, emphasizing the importance of exploring and benchmarking message queues under constrained conditions. Raje highlights the untapped potential in hindering the performance of message queues deliberately, presenting an opportunity to delve deeper into understanding the robustness and adaptability of these systems.

2.7 Chapter Summary

In summary, the literature review based on the outlined structure provides a comprehensive understanding of the comparative study between Kafka and RabbitMQ. By emphasizing traditional and additional performance metrics, challenges, case studies, methodologies, and future directions, the review equips organizations with valuable insights for selecting and optimizing message queue systems based on specific use cases and requirements.

In conclusion, the literature review based on the outlined structure provides a nuanced understanding of Maharjan et al.'s benchmarking study. By focusing on traditional metrics, highlighting limitations, emphasizing the methodological framework, addressing practical use cases, and suggesting future research directions, this review offers a comprehensive overview of the study's contributions to the field of message queue performance evaluation (Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)).

In conclusion, Raje's performance comparison study contributes significantly to the understanding of Apache ActiveMQ, RabbitMQ, and Kafka. By delineating their performance characteristics and acknowledging research limitations, the literature review positions this study as a valuable resource for practitioners seeking to optimize message broker selection in distributed systems. The study's insights and suggestions for future research underscore the evolving landscape of message queuing technologies (Raje, S. (2019)).

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Chapter Overview

"Methodology," outlines the research philosophy, data types, approach, and data collection methods. It emphasizes the selection of pragmatism as the research philosophy and a mixed-method approach to address message queue performance comprehensively. The chapter also discusses the use of Agile methodology in research and outlines the project scope, schedule, resource requirements, and risk management strategies. This methodology chapter forms the backbone of your research, detailing the strategies, tools, and approaches that will guide your project to successful completion.

3.2 Research Methodology

3.2.1 Research Methodology

Layer	What is being using	Why you are using it
philosophy	Pragmatism	<p>Pragmatism is selected because it provides a flexible approach, allowing for the integration of both positivist and interpretivist elements, which is suitable for a project in computer science where both quantitative and qualitative data are valuable.</p> <p>Data Types:</p> <p>Nominal: Categorical data where values have no inherent order, e.g., message queue types.</p> <p>Ordinal: Data with values that have a meaningful order but lack a specific numeric difference, e.g., performance ratings.</p> <p>Interval: Data with a meaningful order and consistent intervals, e.g., response times.</p> <p>Ratio: Interval data with a true zero point, e.g., message queue size.</p>
Approach	Deductive	<p>Deductive research involves starting with existing theories and testing their applicability. In computer science, it allows for testing existing theories, algorithms, or models in novel contexts.</p>
Methodological Choice	Mixed Method	<p>The choice of a mixed-method approach for the research on message queue performance evaluation is appropriate because it allows for a comprehensive understanding of the problem.</p> <p>Message queue performance involves both quantitative (e.g., processing time, memory usage) and qualitative (e.g.,</p>

		<p>reliability, performance) aspects. Using a mixed-method approach helps gather data from both dimensions, enhancing the validity of your research and providing insights into the context and practical implications. This approach is well-suited to address the identified research gap and offers a well-rounded perspective on message queue performance.</p>
<p>Data Collection Strategy</p>	<p>Experiment, Observation, Archival research, Brainstorming</p>	<p>Observation: Observations can be valuable for collecting qualitative data in real-world settings. This might involve observing how message queues are used, monitoring performance in actual systems, and recording how they interact with other components.</p> <p>Experiment: Conducting controlled experiments can help you collect quantitative data under specific conditions. This might involve manipulating variables related to message queue configuration and measuring their impact on performance.</p> <p>Archival Research: Examining existing documentation, performance logs, and historical data can provide valuable insights into how message queues have performed in the past. This archival data can help contextualize the current state of message queue performance.</p> <p>Brainstorming: Brainstorming sessions with a team of experts or stakeholders can help generate ideas and potential performance issues related to message queues. This qualitative approach can be a starting point for identifying research directions.</p>

Time Horizon	Cross section	Research involves collecting data at a single point in time and is primarily focused on a snapshot of message queue performance under specific conditions, then a cross-sectional time horizon would be suitable. This approach provides a snapshot of the current state of message queue performance.
Data Collection and Analysis	Visualization	Create visual representations, such as graphs, charts, and diagrams, to present both quantitative and qualitative findings in a clear and understandable manner.

Table 3.1: Research Methodology

3.2.2 Development Methodology

- Agile Methodology

Agile methodologies are known for their flexibility and adaptability. In a research project, especially one that involves exploring and optimizing message queue systems, agility is essential because research objectives and focus may evolve as gain insights. Agile allows us to adjust to these changes efficiently.

- Methodological Choice

Agile emphasizes incremental and iterative development. Here's how researcher can adapt it to message queue research:

- Sprint Planning

Break down research projects into smaller research tasks or objectives, much like user stories in Agile software development.

- Regular Reviews

At the end of each research "sprint," review the findings, assess the metrics, and adjust the research focus if necessary. This iterative process ensures that researchers are making progress and adapting to findings.

- Adaptability

Agile allows researchers to respond to changes in research objectives or priorities quickly. This is especially useful in a research project, where researchers may discover new avenues for exploration.

- Documentation

Agile typically doesn't mean no documentation. Researchers should still maintain well-organized records of research methods, findings, and changes in direction.

3.3 Project Management Methodology

3.3.1 Project Scope

In Scope

- Evaluation of message queue performance metrics (e.g., memory usage, CPU usage, processing time).
- Assessment of message queue message size.
- Investigation of user experiences and challenges related to message queue usage.
- Development of a comprehensive message queue performance evaluation framework.
- Data collection and analysis using a mixed-method approach.

Out of Scope

- In-depth examination of specific message queue software or platforms (e.g., Kafka, RabbitMQ) unless necessary for the broader context.
- Implementation or modification of message queue systems (focus is on evaluation).

3.3.2 Diagram depicting the prototype feature

Figure 3.1: basic diagram

3.3.3 Gantt Chart

Task ID	Task	Start	Due	Start on Day*	Duration*
4	Define Project Scope	10/6/2023	10/13/2023	0	7
5	Establish Project Objectives	10/13/2023	10/17/2023	7	4
6	Identify Stakeholders	10/17/2023	10/24/2023	11	7
7	Develop Project Charter	10/17/2023	10/28/2023	11	7
8	Conduct Literature Review on Message Queues	10/12/2023	11/2/2023	0	21
9	Define Research Questions	10/4/2023	11/30/2023	27	28
10	Develop Research Methodology	12/1/2023	12/25/2023	50	24
11	Identify Relevant Performance Metrics	12/1/2023	12/30/2023	50	29
12	Obtaining feedback for draft literature review	12/25/2023	12/29/2023	80	4
13	Set Up Testing Environment	12/25/2023	2/22/2024	84	59
14	Select Message Queue Systems for Evaluation	10/17/2023	1/19/2024	11	94
15	Collect Baseline Performance Data	12/25/2023	2/28/2024	80	65
16	Implement Data Collection Tools	12/25/2023	2/22/2024	80	59
17	Obtain the mentor feedback	1/1/2024	1/26/2024	87	25
18	Change architecture based on mentor feedback	1/20/2024	1/26/2024	100	6
19	Submission of SRS	1/27/2024	1/27/2024	113	1
20	Install and setup environment(Docker/ Kafak/ Rabb...	12/25/2023	3/1/2024	80	68
21	Implement java source code to identify and contro...	2/10/2024	3/30/2024	127	49
22	Document the implementation	2/17/2024	5/2/2024	134	75
23	Obtain the mentor feedback	2/22/2024	3/2/2024	139	9
24	Change implementation based on mentor feedback	2/1/2024	3/20/2024	118	58
25	Initial Project Specifications Design and Prototype	2/28/2024	2/28/2024	145	0
26	Creating a test plan	2/22/2024	4/1/2024	139	39
27	Document test result	3/6/2024	3/31/2024	152	25
28	Final evaluation and analysis of the test result	3/6/2024	3/31/2024	152	25
29	Preparing final thesis	4/1/2024	5/28/2024	178	55
30	Obtaining mentor feedback	4/5/2024	5/28/2024	182	51
31	Refine the final thesis base on the suggestion mad...	4/6/2024	5/27/2024	183	51
32	Self evaluation of the final thesis	4/6/2024	5/28/2024	183	52
33	Submission of the final thesis	5/27/2024	6/2/2024	234	0
34	Obtaining mentor feedback	4/6/2024	5/27/2024	183	51
35	Refine the final thesis base on the suggestion mad...	4/6/2024	5/28/2024	183	52
36	Self evaluation of the final thesis	5/27/2024	6/2/2024	234	0
37	Submission of the final thesis	6/2/2024	6/4/2024	240	0

Figure 3.2: Gantt chart

3.3.4 Deliverables and date

Deliverable	Date
Final project proposal submission	26 Oct 2023
LR Submission	20 Dec 2023
SRS Submission	27 Jan 2024
Proof Of Concept Initial proof-of-concept of the proposed work.	15 Feb 2024
Initial Project Specifications Design and Prototype (PSDP) Submission	28 Feb 2024
Minimum Viable Product Submission	4 April 2024
Final Thesis Final Thesis document detailing all processes and findings related to the completed research project Submitting a conference paper based on research findings.	20 May 2024

Table 3.2: Deliverable and date

3.4 Resource requirements

3.4.1 Hardware requirement

- Intel core i5
- 16GB RAM
- 256 SSD hard disk, 1TB hard disk

3.4.2 Software Requirement

- Operating System - Necessary for running essential programs like IDEs and other required tools.
- Java - The main programming language utilized in developing the proposed systems.
- Docker - Employed to enhance the efficiency of the development process.
- Kafka/ zookeeper servers - Used for the implementation of Kafka servers.
- RabbitMq/ ActiveMQ - Employed for implementing RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ servers.
- Zotero - Utilized for organizing, managing, and backing up relevant research papers.
- MS Office - Employed for creating project-related documents.
- Google Drive - Used for backing up project-related files.
- Git/GitHub - Utilized for version control and backup of the application code.
- IntelliJ Idea - Chosen as the Java Integrated Development Environment (IDE).
- python/ Jupyter notebook - Analyze and visualize collected data.

3.4.3 Skill requirements – Hard skills – technical skills

- Installation of required software(Docker)
- Installation of message queue
- Knowledge of Java
- Creative writing skills
- Python scripting language

3.5 Risk Management

Risk is an inherent part of any project, whether it's rooted in theory, technical complexities, or environmental factors. It's crucial to recognize these potential risks, understand their unique characteristics, and establish effective strategies to address and overcome them in a well-organized and resource-efficient manner.

Risk Item	Severity	Frequency	Mitigation Plan
Data loss - There is a risk of data loss during experiments, impacting the accuracy of performance evaluations.	4	5	Use cloud based storage like google drive
System Instability - Implementing enhancements may introduce instability or unexpected behavior in message queue systems. factors.	4	4	Conduct thorough testing in a controlled environment, gradually introducing enhancements. Rollback procedures should be in place if instability occurs.
Resource Constraints - Limited resources (hardware, computing power) may affect the load testing and overall reliability of results.	4	4	Clearly define resource requirements and limitations in the project plan. Consider cloud services for scalable resources if needed.

<p>Unpredictable External Factors – External factors (e.g., network issues, server outages) may impact experiments.</p>	5	3	Conduct experiments in a controlled environment, and document any external factors that influence results.
<p>Limited Generalization – Findings may have limited generalization to other message queue systems or real-world scenarios.</p>	3	3	Clearly define the scope and limitations of the study. Acknowledge potential constraints and encourage further research for broader applicability.

Table 3.3: Risk Management

3.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter details the methodologies used in the research, development, and project management of the message queue research project. It begins with a general overview, followed by the research methodology where the selection of each layer is justified without delving into theoretical definitions. The development methodology section explains the chosen approach and reasons for its preference over others. Project management strategies are discussed, including the schedule outlined through a Gantt chart and key deliverables. The resources section lists the necessary hardware, software, and technical skills acquired, alongside data requirements. The chapter concludes with an assessment of potential risks and their mitigation strategies, and a brief summary.

CHAPTER 4: SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

4.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter provides an in-depth understanding of the software requirements for the research project focused on exploring additional performance matrices in message queues. It outlines the key components and structure of the SRS document, offering a roadmap for stakeholders and readers to navigate through the project's requirements and objectives.

4.2 Rich picture diagram

Figure 4.1: Rich Diagram

4.3 Stakeholder Analysis

4.3.1 Stakeholder Onion Model Diagram

Figure 4.2: Stakeholder Diagram

4.3.2 Analysis of the Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Role	Description
The Project Stakeholders		
Research Team	Researchers and Data Analysts	The research team conducts the evaluation of additional performance metrics in message queues. They design experiments, collect data, analyze results, and draw conclusions to contribute to the body of knowledge in this field.
System Administrators	Manage the system	Teams building applications that produce and consume messages from the queue. High influence through design choices and usage patterns.
Containing System Stakeholders		
Internal Team Members	IT Support Staff	IT support staff provide technical assistance and troubleshooting for users encountering issues with the message queue system.
University Department	Academic Faculty and Researchers	The university department, comprising academic faculty and researchers, contributes to the research project through intellectual guidance, mentorship, and access to research facilities. They provide expertise in relevant fields such as computer science, data analysis, and system performance evaluation, enriching the research with academic rigor and depth.
Industry Partners	Business Stakeholders and Technology	Industry partners collaborate with the research team to provide industry-specific insights, use cases, and resources. They may offer financial support, access to proprietary systems, or domain expertise, ensuring that the research

	Providers	remains relevant and applicable to real-world scenarios.
Software Developers and Partners	Development Teams and Integration Specialists	Software developers and partners play a crucial role in integrating message queue systems into various software applications and platforms. They contribute to the research project by providing feedback on system performance, identifying areas for improvement, and implementing solutions based on the research findings. Their involvement ensures that the research outcomes translate into practical benefits for end users and stakeholders.
Academic Peers and Collaborations	Researchers and Scholars in Related Fields	Academic peers and collaborators engage with the research project through peer review, collaborative research endeavors, and knowledge exchange.
Wider Environment Stakeholders		
Technology Communities	Online Forums and User Groups	Technology communities provide a platform for knowledge sharing and collaboration among professionals interested in message queue systems. They may discuss and disseminate the research findings within their communities.
Regulatory bodies	Government agencies, compliance officers	Entities responsible for setting and enforcing industry regulations and standards that the project must comply with.

Table 4.1: Analysis of the Stakeholders

4.4 Selection of Requirement Elicitation Methodologies

Requirement elicitation is a crucial step in any research project, as it helps gather and define the project's objectives, scope, and specific requirements. The research project on exploring additional performance metrics in message queues (Kafka, RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ), here are requirement elicitation methodologies:

Method 1: Literature Review
In the context of your research project on exploring additional performance metrics in message queues (Kafka, RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ), a literature review serves as a foundational step to gather information, identify gaps, and inform the direction the research
Method 2: Interviews
Conduct interviews with key stakeholders, including developers, system administrators, and researchers, to gather insights on their expectations and requirements regarding performance metrics. Ask open-ended questions to encourage detailed responses.
Method 3: Prototyping
Develop prototypes or mockups of the message queue systems with potential performance metrics incorporated. Use these prototypes to gather feedback from stakeholders about the usability and effectiveness of the proposed metrics.
Method 4: Observation
Observe the current usage of message queue systems in real-world scenarios. This can provide valuable insights into the existing challenges and areas where additional performance metrics may be beneficial.

Table 4.2: Elicitation

4.5 Discussion of Findings through Different Elicitation Methodologies

4.5.1 Literature Review

Finding	Citation
Exploring additional performance metrics beyond latency and throughput would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the strengths and weaknesses. This could include factors such as persistence, scalability, fault tolerance, and resource utilization.	Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)
Frequent communication between services in microservices via synchronous HTTP can reduce the system performance.	Waseem, M., Liang, P., & Shahin, M. (2020)
In recent years, EDA has been widely used in several domains such as network intrusion detection, sensor networks, stock market, fast trading, real time system control, healthcare monitoring, mobile and wearable computing. The main reason is that EDA provides solutions for developing distributed systems that facilitate high flexibility and concurrency.	Tragatschnig, S., Stevanetic, S., & Zdun, U. (2018)
Considering the integration and interoperability aspects of these message queues with other technologies and frameworks commonly used in distributed systems would be beneficial for practitioners seeking to leverage them in real-world applications	Maharjan, R., Chy, M.S.H., Arju, M.A., & Cerny, T. (2023)

Table 4.3: Literature Review

4.5.2. Interview

Theme	Criteria	Analysis
The Importance of Real-Time Monitoring	Stakeholder Insights	The criticality of having access to live data regarding the performance of message queues. Real-time monitoring allows developers to make immediate decisions based on the current state of the system, which is crucial for maintaining optimal performance and quickly addressing any issues that arise.
Scalability and Resource Management	Understanding of Current Pain Points & Concerns about Scalability	Scalability emerges as a significant concern among stakeholders, particularly regarding how the system manages resources under heavy loads and the potential overhead introduced by new metrics. This theme captures the balancing act between enhancing monitoring capabilities and ensuring the system can scale efficiently without degrading performance.
Identification and Prioritization of Key Metrics	Identified Key Metrics	This theme reflects the stakeholders' perspective on what metrics are essential for a comprehensive understanding of message queue performance. It highlights a consensus on the need to monitor fundamental resources (CPU, memory, network) to ensure the health and efficiency of the system. The emphasis on these metrics suggests a prioritization based on their direct impact on system performance and stability.
Balancing Performance and Scalability	Concerns about Scalability &	The need for real-time monitoring and the concerns regarding scalability, illustrating a complex challenge: how to enhance monitoring capabilities without

	Stakeholder Insights	compromising the system's ability to scale. Stakeholders are aware of the benefits of additional metrics but are cautious about the potential performance trade-offs.
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Table 4.4: Interview

4.5.3. Prototyping

Criteria	Findings
Ease of Use	Stakeholders found the prototype intuitive, with a user-friendly interface that facilitated exploration of performance metrics.
Functionality	The prototype effectively simulated the behavior of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, providing a realistic environment for testing and analysis.
Interactivity	Stakeholders appreciated the interactive features of the prototype, allowing them to adjust parameters and observe real-time changes in performance metrics.
Feedback Mechanism	The prototype included a feedback mechanism, and stakeholders provided valuable insights on the relevance and usability of the proposed metrics.
Necessary Adjustments	Identification of any necessary changes or improvements to the metrics.

Table 4.5: Prototyping

4.5.4 Observation

Criteria	Findings
Real-world Usage Patterns	Understanding of how message queues are used in actual scenarios.
Bottlenecks and	Identification of performance bottlenecks and resource utilization.

Resource Usage	
User Behavior	Observations on how users interact with message queues and metrics.

Table 4.6: Observation

4.6 Summary of Findings

Id	Finding	Literature Review	Interviews	Prototyping	Observation
1	Existing Performance Metrics	X	X		X
2	User Preferences		X		X
3	Novel Metric Ideas	X	X	X	X
4	Challenges and Pain Points	X	X	X	X
5	Usability of Metrics			X	X
6	Real-world Usage Patterns	X	X		X
7	Bottlenecks and Resource Usage	X	X	X	X
8	User Behavior		X	X	X
9	Industry Standards		X		X

Table 4.6: Summary Of Findings

4.7 Context Diagram

Figure 4.3: Context Diagram

4.8 Use Case Diagram

Figure 4.4: Use Case Diagram

4.9 Use Case Description

Use case name	Publish Message
ID	UC1
Description	A producer sends a message to be reliably delivered to a consumer via the message queue.
Participating Actors	Producer
Preconditions	The producer is connected to the message queue
Extended Use Cases	
Included Use Cases	(Optional) Validate Message
Main Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The producer creates a message.2. (Optional) If 'Validate Message' is included: The message queue producer validates the message.3. The producer sends the message to the message queue.4. The message queue stores the message.
Exceptional Flows	If the message queue is unavailable, the producer may retry or wait for message queue availability. Sending the message or handling the error according to its error handling logic.
Post Conditions	The message is either stored in the message queue or the producer is notified of an error.

Table 4.7: Use Case Description

4.10 Requirement specification

Priority Level	Description
Must have (M)	The requirements that are important and essential to develop a successful Minimum Viable Product (MVP).
Should have (S)	The requirements that are important but not essential to develop a successful MVP. But the system will have some limitations.
Could have (C)	The requirements that are desirable but not essential to develop a successful MVP.
Will not have (W)	The requirements that are not developed during the initial stage of MVP.

Table 4.8: Requirement Specification

4.10.1 Functional Requirements

S. No	Functional Requirement	Priority	Use case Mapping
1	The system must support the exploration of additional performance metrics for Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ.	M	1,4
2	Metrics data must be stored securely and be accessible for analysis and reporting.	M	2,4
3	The system should provide visualizations and graphs for performance metrics trends over time.	S	2
4	It should support the export of performance metric data for further analysis.	S	2,3,4
5	The system could integrate with external monitoring tools for enhanced analytics.	C	2
6	It could provide predictive analytics based on historical performance data.	C	3,4

Table 4.9: Functional Requirements

4.10.2 Non Functional Requirements

S. No	Non-Functional Requirement	Description	Priority
1	Reliability	The ability to persist messages, guaranteeing they are not lost even in the event of system failures or outages.	M
2	Performance	Minimizing the delay between when a message is sent and when it is received and processed. Optimizing memory and CPU consumption to keep operational costs down, especially under heavy load.	M
3	Usability	Comprehensive documentation and examples to support the integration process. Dashboards and metrics to provide visibility into queue health and performance.	S
4	Maintainability	Clear separation of components to facilitate updates and fixes.	S
5	Compliance	Ability to track system events and access for compliance investigations. Mechanisms to adhere to data retention policies required by relevant regulations.	C
6	Real-Time Analytics	Mechanisms for rapid access to message data for real-time processing.	W

Table 4.10: Non Functional Requirements

4.11 Chapter Summary

The requirement specification chapter serves as a comprehensive guide outlining the objectives, scope, and specific needs of the research project on exploring additional performance metrics in message queues (Kafka, RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ). The document employs the MoSCoW technique to categorize and prioritize both functional and non-functional requirements. The use case descriptions further detail essential functionalities, such as exploring metrics, configuring thresholds, and viewing metric reports. This requirement specification chapter serves as a foundational document for guiding the subsequent phases of the research project, providing a clear roadmap for implementation and evaluation.

CHAPTER 5: Social, Legal, Ethical and Professional issues (SLEP)

5.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter provides an in-depth analysis of the social, legal, ethical, and professional issues associated with the research project. It begins by outlining the broader context and importance of addressing SLEP issues in research. The subsequent sections detail the specific social, legal, ethical, and professional challenges encountered during the project, along with the strategies implemented to mitigate these issues. The chapter concludes with a summary of the key points discussed.

5.2 SLEP Issues and Mitigation

5.2.1 Social Issues

The research involved the collection and analysis of performance data from Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ systems. Ensuring the privacy and security of this data was paramount. Although the data did not include personally identifiable information (PII). Ensured that all data used for analysis was anonymized and did not contain any sensitive information.

5.2.2 Legal Issues

While the research did not involve personal data, there is no restriction in data from a legal perspective.

Using specific software versions of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ necessitated adherence to their respective licenses and intellectual property rights. Ensured that all software used in the research was properly licensed or open source. Adhered to the terms and conditions of use specified by the software providers, and properly cited any third-party tools or libraries used.

5.3.3 Ethical Issues

If any interviews or personal interactions had been conducted as part of the research, obtaining written consent would have been crucial. However, this research primarily involved technical data collection and analysis without direct interaction with individuals. In cases where hypothetical interviews or personal interactions might have occurred, prepared consent forms

and protocols to obtain written consent. Ensured transparency with any participants regarding the purpose, scope, and use of the collected data.

5.3.4 Professional Issues

The research project adhered to the BCS Code of Conduct, which emphasizes professional competence, integrity, and responsibility. Ensuring that the research was conducted with professionalism and integrity was a key consideration. Maintained a high level of professional competence by continuously updating knowledge and skills relevant to the research. Acted with integrity by being honest and trustworthy in all research activities. Took responsibility for the research, ensuring that it was conducted ethically and professionally at all times.

Properly acknowledging the contributions of others and collaborating effectively with peers and advisors was essential to maintain professional standards. Gave appropriate credit to all contributors and collaborators.

Ensured open and respectful communication with peers, advisors, and any stakeholders involved in the research.

5.4 Chapter Summary

This chapter addressed the social, legal, ethical, and professional issues encountered during the research project on message queue systems. By adhering to the BCS Code of Conduct, the research maintained high standards of integrity, responsibility, and professionalism. Specific strategies were implemented to mitigate social issues related to data privacy, legal issues concerning data protection and intellectual property, ethical issues around data integrity and consent, and professional issues ensuring adherence to the BCS Code of Conduct. These measures ensured that the research was conducted ethically, legally, and professionally, contributing to its overall credibility and reliability.

CHAPTER 6: DESIGN

6.1 Chapter overview

This chapter establishes the blueprint for the 'Explore Additional Performance Metrics Message Queue' research project. It outlines essential design goals (quality attributes) that guide the architectural choices. The system's high-level architecture is presented visually, with a discussion of its tiers/layers. Next, the chapter delves into low-level design, justifying the selection of an appropriate design paradigm. Finally, detailed design diagrams, including component diagrams and methodology-specific diagrams (UML or DFDs), provide a comprehensive view of the system's structure.

6.2 Design Goals

Design Goal	Description
Accuracy	The metrics should reflect the true underlying performance of the message queue with minimal deviation or noise.
Reliability	The metrics should produce consistent results across multiple test runs under similar conditions.
Granularity	The metrics should provide fine-grained detail, allowing to pinpoint specific performance bottlenecks or optimization opportunities within the message queue.
Configurability	The metrics framework should allow adjustment of parameters to control the type and depth of data collected.
Environmental Sensitivity	The metrics should be able to account for variations in workload, network conditions, hardware configurations, or other factors that might influence message queue performance.

Ease of Use	The metrics framework should be intuitive to set up, run, and interpret, minimizing the learning curve and potential errors.
Interpretability	The metrics should be presented in a clear, meaningful format that facilitates decision-making about optimization strategies.

Table 6.1: Design Goals

6.3 High level Design/ System Architecture Design

6.3.1 Architecture Diagram

Figure 6.1: Architecture Diagram

6.3.2 Discussion of tiers/ layers of the Architecture

Begin with an overview of your system's architecture, emphasizing the importance of structuring it into distinct layers. Mention the objective of exploring additional performance metrics in message queues and how this architectural design facilitates achieving that goal.

Application Layer

This tier consists of Java spring boot applications running within Docker containers, fulfilling both message producer and consumer roles. Three sets of producer/consumer pairs are implemented, with each set interacting with a specific message queue configuration (Kafka, RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ). Containerization ensures consistent deployment environments across the different messaging systems.

Messaging Layer

This crucial tier comprises the core message brokers – Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. These brokers provide the messaging backbone, facilitating asynchronous communication, message persistence, and routing between the producers and consumers in the application tier.

Logging/Monitoring Tier

JMeter: JMeter's open-source nature makes it freely available and JMeter simulates heavy user loads on a server, network, or object to identify bottlenecks and analyze a system's performance under various conditions.

6.4 Low-level Design/ System Design

6.4.1 Choice of design paradigm

Object-Oriented Foundations: Java is an object-oriented programming (OOP) language. Its core principles revolve around concepts like classes, objects, inheritance, polymorphism, and encapsulation.

Natural Modeling: OOADM provides a framework for analyzing and designing the system in terms of real-world entities (modeled as objects), their attributes (data), and behaviors (methods). This maps directly to the programming constructs available in Java.

Code Maintainability and Reusability: OOP and OOADM promote the creation of modular, well-defined components that can be easily understood, updated, and reused. This is essential for managing complexity as message queue metrics projects evolve.

Since the project is implemented in Java, the most suitable design paradigm is OOADM (Object-Oriented Analysis and Design Methodology)

6.5 Design Diagrams

6.5.1 Component Diagram

Figure 6.2: Component Diagram

6.5.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 6.3: Activity Diagram

6.5.3 Class diagram

Figure 6.4: Class Diagram

6.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter defined the blueprint for the "Explore Additional Performance Metrics in Message Queue" system. To ensure accurate and adaptable measurements, key design goals were identified. A tiered architecture was chosen for modularity, and its layers were discussed in detail. Finally, an object-oriented design paradigm (OOADM) was selected for its alignment with Java, and a component diagram illustrated the system's software structure.

CHAPTER 7: IMPLEMENTATION

7.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter translates the architectural blueprint into a tangible implementation of the "Explore Additional Performance Metrics in Message Queue" project. It begins with a detailed exploration of the chosen technology stack, justifying the selection of frontend, middleware, and backend components. Development frameworks, programming languages, essential libraries, and the integrated development environment (IDE) will be outlined, with explanations for each choice. A tabular summary will synthesize these selections. Next, the chapter presents the implementation of core system functionality, providing code examples in image format.

7.2 Technology Selection

This section outlines the key technologies chosen for the "Explore Additional Performance Metrics in Message Queue" project and provides justifications for their selection.

7.2.1 Technology Stack

Figure 7.1: Technology Stack

7.2.2 Development Framework

Framework	Purpose	Justification
Spring Boot	Application framework, web services, dependency injection	Simplifies development, provides robust infrastructure

Table 7.1: Development Framework

7.2.3 Programming Languages

Language	Purpose	Justification
Java 17	Core application logic, metric collection	Object-oriented, robust, extensive libraries, JVM-based

Python	Analyze and visualize data	Jupyter Notebook is a powerful and flexible tool for data analysis and visualization
--------	----------------------------	--

Table 7.2: Programming Languages

7.2.4 Libraries

Library	Purpose	Justification
Spring Boot	Application framework, web services, dependency injection	Simplifies development, provides robust infrastructure
Kafka/RMQ/AMQ Clients	Interaction with message queues	Provides API for message production and consumption
Logback	Logging, troubleshooting, audit trail	Flexible configuration, diverse appenders

Table 7.3: Libraries

7.2.5 IDE

IDE	Justification
IntelliJ IDEA	Advanced Java support, debugging, refactoring, integration with build tools and version control
jupyter notebook	Can process and visualize data easily

Table 7.4: IDE

7.2.6 Summary of Technology Selection

Technology/Layer	Component	Purpose
Test Layer	Jmeter	Load generation, test configuration, visualization
Middleware	Java 17	Programming language foundation
Backend	Spring Boot 3	Application framework, REST API creation
Containerization	Docker 24.0.7+	Deployment and environment consistency

Version Control	Git - 2.25.1 / GitHub	Code management, collaboration
Process data	Jupyter Notebook	Dara visualize/ process
Message queue	Kafka/ Zookeeper - 7.6.0 Rabbit MQ - 5.18.3 Active MQ - 3.9.29-management	Message queue server

Table 7.5: Summary Of Technology Selection

7.3 Implementation of the Core Functionality

7.3.1 Kafka

Producer:

```

15  @Configuration
16  public class KafkaProducerConfig { kavindu, 2/14/24, 7:42 AM • feat:
17
18      @Value("${spring.kafka.bootstrap-servers}")
19      private String bootstrapServers;
20
21      Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
22      ± kavindu
23      @Bean
24      public ProducerFactory<String, String> producerFactory() {
25          Map<String, Object> configProps = new HashMap<>();
26          configProps.put(ProducerConfig.BOOTSTRAP_SERVERS_CONFIG, bootstrapServers);
27          configProps.put(ProducerConfig.KEY_SERIALIZER_CLASS_CONFIG, StringSerializer.class);
28          configProps.put(ProducerConfig.VALUE_SERIALIZER_CLASS_CONFIG, StringSerializer.class);
29          return new DefaultKafkaProducerFactory<>(configProps);
30      }
31      Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
32      ± kavindu
33      @Bean
34      public KafkaTemplate<String, String> kafkaTemplate() { return new KafkaTemplate<>(producerFactory()); }

```

Figure 7.1: Kafka Code

This code snippet configures a Spring-managed Kafka producer. It does the following:
 Defines Kafka Producer Settings: Sets up the connection to your Kafka cluster and specifies that both message keys and values will be serialized as strings.

Creates a Producer Factory: Establishes a factory object to build Kafka producers based on the provided configuration.

Instantiates a KafkaTemplate: Provides a convenient Spring bean to simplify the process of sending messages to Kafka within your application.

```
12 @RestController
13 @RequestMapping("/api/messages")
14 public class MessageController {
15
16     @Autowired
17     private KafkaTemplate<String, String> kafkaTemplate;
18
19     @Value("test-topic")
20     private String kafkaTopic;
21
22     @PostMapping
23     public void sendMessageToKafkaTopic(@RequestBody String message) {
24         try {
25             kafkaTemplate.send(kafkaTopic, message);
26         } catch (Exception e) {
27             throw new RuntimeException(HttpStatus.INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR, "Failed to send message to Kafka topic", e);
28         }
29     }
30 }
```

Figure 7.2: Kafka Code

This code snippet defines a REST API endpoint within Spring Boot application. The endpoint accepts HTTP POST requests to /api/messages. The message payload from the request is then sent to the specified Kafka topic using the KafkaTemplate. Basic error handling is implemented to report failures back to the client.

Consumer:

```
15 @Configuration
16 @EnableKafka
17 public class KafkaConfig {
18
19     private final String bootstrapServers = "localhost:9092";
20
21     @Bean
22     public ConsumerFactory<String, String> consumerFactory() {
23         Map<String, Object> props = new HashMap<>();
24         props.put(ConsumerConfig.BOOTSTRAP_SERVERS_CONFIG, bootstrapServers);
25         props.put(ConsumerConfig.GROUP_ID_CONFIG, "group_id");
26         props.put(ConsumerConfig.KEY_DESERIALIZER_CLASS_CONFIG, StringDeserializer.class);
27         props.put(ConsumerConfig.VALUE_DESERIALIZER_CLASS_CONFIG, StringDeserializer.class);
28         return new DefaultKafkaConsumerFactory<>(props);
29     }
30
31     @Bean
32     public ConcurrentKafkaListenerContainerFactory<String, String> kafkaListenerContainerFactory() {
33         ConcurrentKafkaListenerContainerFactory<String, String> factory = new ConcurrentKafkaListenerContainerFactory<>();
34         factory.setConsumerFactory(consumerFactory());
35         return factory;
36     }
37 }
```

Figure 7.3: Kafka Code

This code establishes the necessary configuration to build a Spring-managed Kafka consumer for receiving messages from a Kafka topic.

These code snippets configure the foundational beans to create a Kafka consumer within the Spring Boot application. It sets up the connection to your Kafka cluster, assigns a consumer group ID, specifies string deserialization, and establishes a factory for managing message listener containers.

```

5
  Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
  kavindu
5
@Service
7
public class KafkaListenerService {
3
  kavindu, 1/21/24, 10:14 PM • Initial commit
  Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
  kavindu
7
  @KafkaListener(topics = "test-topic", groupId = "group_id")
3
  public void listen(String message) {
1
    System.out.println("Received Message: " + message);
2
    // Add your business logic here
5
  }
4
}

```

Figure 7.4: Kafka Code

This code snippet defines a Spring service that contains a Kafka message listener. The listener will automatically consume messages from the specified Kafka topic and invoke the listen method for each message. This is where I implement the core logic to handle the received messages according to your system's requirements.

7.3.2 ActiveMq

Producer:

```

6
@Component
7
public class MessageProducer {
8
  2 usages
9
  private final JmsTemplate jmsTemplate;
10
  kavindu
11
  public MessageProducer(JmsTemplate jmsTemplate) {
12
    this.jmsTemplate = jmsTemplate;
13
  }
14
  1 usage  kavindu
15
  public void sendMessage(String message) {
16
    jmsTemplate.convertAndSend(destinationName: "myQueue", message);
17
  }
18
}

```

Figure 7.5: ActiveMQ Code

The MessageProducer class simplifies sending messages to a JMS queue. It takes a pre-configured JmsTemplate bean as a dependency, which handles the underlying JMS interactions. The sendMessage method offers a convenient way to send string messages to a specified queue named "myQueue" within the application.

Consumer:

```
@Configuration
@EnableJms
public class ActiveMQConfig {

    1 usage
    private final String brokerUrl = "tcp://localhost:61616"; // Change this to your ActiveMQ b

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu

    @Bean
    public ActiveMQConnectionFactory connectionFactory() {
        ActiveMQConnectionFactory connectionFactory = new ActiveMQConnectionFactory();
        connectionFactory.setBrokerURL(brokerUrl);
        return connectionFactory;
    }

    kavindu, 1/24/24, 9:08 PM • Add active mq
    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu

    @Bean
    public JmsTemplate jmsTemplate() {
        JmsTemplate jmsTemplate = new JmsTemplate(connectionFactory());
        return jmsTemplate;
    }

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu

    @Bean
    public DefaultJmsListenerContainerFactory jmsListenerContainerFactory() {
        DefaultJmsListenerContainerFactory factory = new DefaultJmsListenerContainerFactory();
        factory.setConnectionFactory(connectionFactory());
        factory.setConcurrency("1-1"); // Set the number of concurrent consumers
        return factory;
    }
}
```

Figure 7.6: ActiveMQ Code

This configuration class establishes the fundamental beans required to interact with an ActiveMQ broker using Spring's JMS support. It provides:

Connection Management: Configures the connection to your ActiveMQ server.

Messaging Template: Provides a simplified JmsTemplate for sending and potentially receiving JMS messages.

Listener Container Factory: Sets up a factory to manage listener containers, which are components that actively listen for and consume incoming messages.

7.3.3 RabbitMq

Producer:

```
    @Bean
    public ConnectionFactory connectionFactory() {
        CachingConnectionFactory connectionFactory = new CachingConnectionFactory(rabbitMQHost, rabbitMQPort);
        connectionFactory.setUsername(rabbitMQUsername);
        connectionFactory.setPassword(rabbitMQPassword);
        return connectionFactory;
    }

    @Bean
    public RabbitTemplate rabbitTemplate() { return new RabbitTemplate(connectionFactory()); }

    @Bean
    public Queue myQueue() { return new Queue( name: "myQueue"); }

    @Bean
    public MeterRegistry meterRegistry() {
        return new SimpleMeterRegistry();
    }
}
```

Figure 7.7: RabbitMQ Code

These bean definitions establish the core configuration for interacting with a RabbitMQ server within a Spring Boot application. They provide beans for managing connections, sending/receiving messages, defining a queue, and potentially setting up metrics collection.

```

@Component
public class RabbitMQProducer {

    2 usages
    private final RabbitTemplate rabbitTemplate;
    2 usages
    private final Counter messagesSentCounter;

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    ⚡ kavindu
    @Autowired
    public RabbitMQProducer(RabbitTemplate rabbitTemplate, MeterRegistry meterRegistry) {
        this.rabbitTemplate = rabbitTemplate;
        this.messagesSentCounter = Counter.builder( name: "rabbitmq.messages.sent")
            .description("Total number of messages sent to RabbitMQ")
            .register(meterRegistry);
    }

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    1 usage ⚡ kavindu
    public void sendMessage(String message) {
        rabbitTemplate.convertAndSend( routingKey: "myQueue", message);
        System.out.println("Message sent to RabbitMQ: " + message);
        messagesSentCounter.increment();
    }
}

```

kavindu, 1/27/24, 9:47 PM • Add rabbit mq producer

Figure 7.8: RabbitMQ Code

The RabbitMQProducer component handles message sending to a RabbitMQ queue. It utilizes a RabbitTemplate for communication and integrates with a MeterRegistry to enable tracking of a 'messages sent' metric.

The MonitoringComponent periodically collects and logs system metrics, including memory usage and CPU utilization. It leverages Java's management APIs to gather these metrics, providing insights into the application's resource consumption.

Consumer:

```

@Configuration
public class RabbitMQConfig {
    1 usage
    private final String rabbitMQHost = "localhost"; // Change this to your RabbitMQ server host
    1 usage
    private final String rabbitMQQueue = "myQueue"; // Change this to your RabbitMQ queue name

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu
    @Bean
    public ConnectionFactory connectionFactory() {
        CachingConnectionFactory connectionFactory = new CachingConnectionFactory(rabbitMQHost);
        // You can add more configuration here if needed
        return connectionFactory;
    }

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu
    @Bean
    public RabbitTemplate rabbitTemplate() { return new RabbitTemplate(connectionFactory()); }

    Explain | Test | Document | Fix | Ask
    kavindu
    @Bean
    public Queue queue() { return new Queue(rabbitMQQueue, durable: true); }
}

```

Figure 7.9: RabbitMQ Code

This RabbitMQConfig class establishes the fundamental configuration for interacting with a RabbitMQ server within the application. It defines beans for managing connections (connectionFactory), simplifying message operations (rabbitTemplate), and declares a RabbitMQ queue (rabbitMQQueue) used for sending and receiving messages.

7.3.4 Jupyter Notebook

The Jupyter Notebook python script is used to analyze and graph the collected data.

```

: # Function to convert memory usage to GiB
def convert_to_gib(value):
    if 'MiB' in value:
        return float(value.replace('MiB', '')) / 1024
    elif 'GiB' in value:
        return float(value.replace('GiB', ''))
    else:
        return float(value)

data['Memory Usage'] = data['Memory Usage'].apply(convert_to_gib)
data_memory = data['Memory Usage']

```

```
# Plotting CPU Usage over time
plt.figure(figsize=(14, 7))
plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)
plt.plot(data['Second'], data['CPU Usage (%)'], marker='o')
plt.title('CPU Usage Over Time')
plt.xlabel('Time (seconds)')
plt.ylabel('CPU Usage (%)')
plt.grid(True)

# Plotting Memory Usage Percentage over time
plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)
plt.plot(data['Second'], data_memory, marker='o', color='r')
plt.title('Memory Usage Percentage Over Time')
plt.xlabel('Time (seconds)')
plt.ylabel('Memory Usage (%)')
plt.grid(True)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Figure 7.9: Jupyter Notebook Code

7.4 Chapter Summary

This chapter outlined the technological foundation and initial implementation of the "Explore Additional Performance Metrics in Message Queue" project. A detailed technology stack was presented, justifying selections across frontend, middleware, and backend layers. Development frameworks, programming languages, libraries, and the IDE were outlined with explanations. The chapter then presented core functionality code snippets (in image format), demonstrating key implementation logic within the chosen technology stack.

CHAPTER 8: TESTING

8.1 chapter overview

This chapter describes the testing methods employed to evaluate the additional performance metrics of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ in terms of CPU and memory usage. It outlines the setup, procedures, and types of tests conducted to ensure comprehensive assessment.

8.2 Objectives and Goals of Testing

The primary objective of the testing phase is to identify and compare the performance of the selected message queues across varying message sizes, focusing on CPU, memory usage metrics and total time taken for the transaction (processing time). This aims to reveal insights into each system's efficiency and resource management capabilities.

8.3 Testing Criteria

The criteria for testing are based on the accuracy and reliability of capturing CPU and memory usage during message processing, ensuring that the data reflects true performance under different loads. Also focus on the time taken for the message delivery.

The test was conducted using push messages of 100 bytes, 10 KB, and 1 KB with a constant 100 TPS for 30 seconds via JMeter to measure CPU and memory usage on the message queue servers. Data was collected for 30 seconds before the load test, then the load was applied for another 30 seconds. Performance data was recorded until all messages were received by the consumer.

8.3.1 Memory and CPU usage calculation

The memory and CPU usages calculate thorough Bash script, which gets the usage data for docker containers, using *docker stats* command. The script is running every seconds and data will be saved as CSV file format.

```
# Fetch stats for the specified container
STATS=$(docker stats --no-stream --format "{{.CPUPerc}},{{.MemUsage}}" $CONTAINER)

# Parse CPU and memory usage
CPU_USAGE=$(echo $STATS | cut -d ',' -f1 | tr -d '%')
MEM_USAGE_RAW=$(echo $STATS | cut -d ',' -f2)
MEM_USAGE=$(echo $MEM_USAGE_RAW | awk '{print $1}')
MEM_LIMIT=$(echo $MEM_USAGE_RAW | awk '{print $3}')

# Convert memory usage and limit from MiB/GiB to bytes for more accurate calculation
MEM_USAGE_BYTES=$(echo $MEM_USAGE | awk '{gsub(/MiB|GiB/, ""); print}')
MEM_LIMIT_BYTES=$(echo $MEM_LIMIT | awk '{gsub(/MiB|GiB/, ""); print}')
    if [[ $MEM_USAGE =~ GiB$ ]]; then MEM_USAGE_BYTES=$(echo
"$MEM_USAGE_BYTES * 1024" | bc); fi
    if [[ $MEM_LIMIT =~ GiB$ ]]; then MEM_LIMIT_BYTES=$(echo "$MEM_LIMIT_BYTES *
1024" | bc); fi

# Calculate memory usage percentage
MEM_PERCENT=$(echo "scale=2; ($MEM_USAGE_BYTES / $MEM_LIMIT_BYTES) *
100" | bc)
```

8.4 Model Testing

In model testing, we examine the theoretical constructs against simulated scenarios to validate our hypothesis regarding performance impact due to changes in message size.

8.4.1 Single producer consumer

A Single producer and consumer scenario used to evaluate the performance of message queue and the messages will be communicated through the specific topic.

Figure 8.1: Single Producer Consumer

8.5 Functional Testing

This involves checking the basic functions of the message queue systems to ensure they perform as expected without any functional failures during the message handling processes. This was tested by sending a sample message to the producer API and checking that the consumer received it via the log details. Additionally, the message queue server's dashboard could verify the status of the transferred messages.

8.6 Module and Integration Testing

Module testing checks individual components (producer, consumer, message queue server) for performance anomalies, while integration testing ensures that these components work together seamlessly under test conditions.

8.7 Non functional Testing

Focuses on the stability, usability, and reliability of the message queues and producer/ consumer java applications, particularly looking at how they manage resources under stress and normal conditions.

This section presents initial benchmark results focusing on RabbitMQ performance under a load of 100 transactions per second (TPS) with varying message sizes. The primary metrics analyzed are CPU and memory usage.

8.7.1 Test Setup 01

Test Case	RQ1_TC01
Description	Message throughput with small messages
Scalability	Single Prod/Cons
Message Size	100 bytes
Workload	100 TPS
Component monitored	RabbitMQ Server, Kafka Server, ActiveMQ Server

Table 8.1: Test Setup 01

Key Observations

ActiveMQ

Figure 8.2: ActiveMQ test 01

RabbitMQ

Figure 8.3: RabbitMQ test 01

Kafka

Figure 8.4: Kafka test 01

Metrics	Rabbit mq	Active mq	Kafka
Mean CPU Usage	34.628571	27.341538	8.51871
Median CPU Usage	44.77	34.73	1.27
Max CPU Usage	67.15	96.9	135.24
Min CPU Usage	0.22	0.15	0.79
STD CPU Usage	24.818675	19.661754	22.241276
Mean Memory Usage	0.141247	0.234869	0.452379
Median Memory Usage	0.141602	0.244336	0.45791

Max Memory Usage	0.143359	0.24541	0.463477
Min Memory Usage	0.138867	0.180078	0.410547
STD Memory Usage	0.001255	0.021994	0.014058
95th Percentile CPU Usage	63.066	51.115	50.608
99th Percentile CPU Usage	65.79	82.6186	97.2256
95th Percentile Memory Usage	0.142666	0.245312	0.458203
99th Percentile Memory Usage	0.143193	0.24541	0.458625
Time seconds	124	692	330

Table 8.2: Test Result 01

In this test case focusing on message throughput with small messages (100 bytes) at 100 transactions per second, Kafka demonstrates the lowest mean CPU usage at 8.52%, indicating its efficiency in handling CPU resources under the given workload. RabbitMQ has the highest mean CPU usage at 34.63%, suggesting a higher demand on CPU resources compared to the other systems. ActiveMQ shows a moderate mean CPU usage of 27.34%. The median CPU usage values further highlight Kafka's efficiency with a low median of 1.27%, significantly lower than RabbitMQ's 44.77% and ActiveMQ's 34.73%. However, Kafka exhibits the highest peak CPU usage at 135.24%, indicating occasional spikes under heavy load, whereas RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ have lower peak usages of 67.15% and 96.9%, respectively. The standard deviation (STD) of CPU usage is highest for RabbitMQ at 24.82%, followed by Kafka at 22.24% and ActiveMQ at 19.66%, indicating variability in performance across different intervals.

RabbitMQ excels in memory efficiency, demonstrating the lowest mean memory usage at 0.1412%, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.2349% and Kafka's 0.4524%. This trend continues with the median memory usage, where RabbitMQ again shows the lowest value at 0.1416%, followed by

ActiveMQ at 0.2443% and Kafka at 0.4579%. The maximum memory usage is also lowest for RabbitMQ at 0.1434%, indicating consistent memory consumption, whereas ActiveMQ and Kafka peak at 0.2454% and 0.4635%, respectively. RabbitMQ's minimal baseline memory usage is evident from its lowest minimum memory usage of 0.1389%, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.1801% and Kafka's 0.4105%. The standard deviation (STD) of memory usage is lowest for RabbitMQ at 0.0013%, indicating highly stable performance, followed by Kafka at 0.0141% and ActiveMQ at 0.0220%, suggesting moderate variability in memory usage.

Examining the high-percentile CPU usage, RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ show higher values in the 95th and 99th percentiles, with RabbitMQ at 63.07% and 65.79%, and ActiveMQ at 51.12% and 82.62%, respectively. Kafka's 95th percentile CPU usage is 50.61%, while its 99th percentile is significantly higher at 97.23%, indicating occasional high spikes in CPU usage. For memory usage, the 95th percentile values for RabbitMQ, ActiveMQ, and Kafka are 0.1427%, 0.2453%, and 0.4582%, respectively, with the 99th percentile values being very close at 0.1432%, 0.2454%, and 0.4586%, respectively. This consistency in high-percentile memory usage further highlights RabbitMQ's efficiency and stability compared to the other systems.

RabbitMQ completes the task of delivering all messages in the shortest time of 124 seconds, demonstrating its efficiency and speed in handling small messages at high throughput. Kafka takes significantly longer at 330 seconds, while ActiveMQ is the slowest, taking 692 seconds. This substantial difference indicates that RabbitMQ is highly optimized for quick message delivery, making it suitable for applications requiring low latency and fast processing times. Kafka's moderate performance suggests it can handle the workload efficiently but may experience delays under peak conditions. ActiveMQ's prolonged delivery time indicates potential inefficiencies or limitations in handling small messages at high throughput, highlighting areas for further optimization.

8.7.2 Test Setup 02

Test Case	RQ1_TC02
Description	Throughput comparison with large messages,
Scalability	Single Prod/Cons
Message Size	10 kb
Workload	100 TPS
Component monitored	RabbitMQ Server, Kafka Server, ActiveMQ Server

Table 8.3: Test Case 02

ActiveMQ

Figure 8.5: ActiveMQ test 02

RabbitMQ

Figure 8.6: RabbitMQ test 02

Kafka

Figure 8.7: Kafka test 02

Metrics	Rabbit mq	Active mq	Kafka
Mean CPU Usage	2.452664	1.295841	2.091619
Median CPU Usage	0.43	0.19	1.01
Max CPU Usage	86.52	107.05	95.13
Min CPU Usage	0.18	0.12	0.71
STD CPU Usage	8.31345	5.094617	8.445715
Mean Memory Usage	0.417384	1.071884	1.176102
Median Memory Usage	0.264355	1.081	1.208
Max Memory Usage	1.132	1.131	1.393
Min Memory Usage	0.07876	0.190625	0.404004
STD Memory Usage	0.360025	0.07644	0.152313
95th Percentile CPU Usage	5.821	2.78	1.6905
99th Percentile CPU Usage	44.8312	26.26	57.7818
95th Percentile Memory Usage	1.037	1.114	1.362
99th Percentile Memory Usage	1.05882	1.126	1.386
Time spent to deliver all the messages(seconds)	10349	18874	10450

Table 8.4: Test Result 02

In this test case, which focuses on the throughput comparison with large messages (10 KB) at 100 transactions per second, ActiveMQ demonstrates the lowest mean CPU usage at 1.30%, indicating its efficiency in handling CPU resources. RabbitMQ, with a mean CPU usage of 2.45%, and Kafka, with 2.09%, consume more CPU on average compared to ActiveMQ. The median CPU usage further highlights ActiveMQ's efficiency, with a median of 0.19%, compared to RabbitMQ's 0.43% and Kafka's 1.01%. However, ActiveMQ exhibits the highest peak CPU usage at 107.05%, suggesting occasional spikes, whereas RabbitMQ and Kafka peak at 86.52% and 95.13%, respectively. The standard deviation (STD) of CPU usage is lowest for ActiveMQ at 5.09%, indicating more consistent performance, while RabbitMQ and Kafka have higher variability with STDs of 8.31% and 8.45%, respectively.

RabbitMQ excels in memory efficiency with a mean memory usage of 0.42%, which is significantly lower than ActiveMQ's 1.07% and Kafka's 1.18%. The median memory usage also places RabbitMQ in the lead at 0.26%, compared to ActiveMQ's 1.08% and Kafka's 1.21%. While the maximum memory usage is comparable across all three systems, RabbitMQ's lowest minimum memory usage of 0.08% indicates minimal baseline memory consumption. ActiveMQ's lower variability in memory usage, with an STD of 0.08%, suggests more stable performance, whereas RabbitMQ and Kafka show higher variability with STDs of 0.36% and 0.15%, respectively. The 95th and 99th percentile values further illustrate RabbitMQ's efficiency, as it has the lowest high-percentile memory usage.

RabbitMQ and Kafka are relatively close in terms of the time taken to deliver all messages, with RabbitMQ slightly faster at 10,349 seconds compared to Kafka's 10,450 seconds. This efficiency makes RabbitMQ particularly suitable for scenarios requiring timely message delivery. ActiveMQ, however, takes significantly longer to deliver all messages at 18,874 seconds, indicating potential inefficiencies or limitations in processing large messages efficiently. The prolonged delivery time for ActiveMQ could be a major drawback for applications that demand quick processing and delivery of large volumes of messages.

Regarding CPU efficiency, ActiveMQ demonstrates the lowest mean and median CPU usage but shows higher maximum usage and variability, indicating occasional performance spikes. Kafka stands out in handling high loads efficiently, as evidenced by its lower 95th percentile CPU

usage. For memory efficiency, RabbitMQ consistently uses less memory across all metrics, showcasing its superior memory management capabilities. In terms of message delivery time, RabbitMQ is the fastest, closely followed by Kafka, whereas ActiveMQ's significantly longer delivery time could be a critical disadvantage in high-performance applications. Overall, RabbitMQ and Kafka are more efficient in terms of CPU and memory usage, with ActiveMQ showing potential but also having notable limitations.

8.7.3 Test Setup 03

Test Case	RQ1_TC03
Description	Throughput comparison with large messages,
Scalability	Single Prod/Cons
Message Size	1 kb
Workload	100 TPS
Component monitored	RabbitMQ Server, Kafka Server, ActiveMQ Server

Table 8.5: Test Case 03

Activemq

Figure 8.8: ActiveMQ test 03

Rabbitmq

Figure 8.9: RabbitMQ test 03

Kafka

Figure 8.10: Kafka test 03

Metrics	Rabbit mq	Active mq	Kafka
Mean CPU Usage	13.824161	10.422671	3.431144
Median CPU Usage	0.77	0.305	1.23
Max CPU Usage	91.25	130.78	119.3
Min CPU Usage	0.19	0.13	0.81
STD CPU Usage	21.676934	14.816735	11.587207
Mean Memory Usage	0.875903	0.786112	0.489384
Median Memory Usage	0.94585	0.882227	0.490332
Max Memory Usage	1.286	0.887695	0.527148
Min Memory Usage	0.128223	0.179004	0.368262
STD Memory Usage	0.178531	0.178575	0.034797
95th Percentile CPU Usage	57.5765	35.2965	4.74
99th Percentile CPU Usage	66.0524	56.0286	69.328

95th Percentile Memory Usage	0.984326	0.886816	0.526943
99th Percentile Memory Usage	1.07053	0.887598	1.386
Time spent to deliver all the messages(seconds)	3349	2806	1460

Table 8.6: Test Result 03

In this test case focusing on throughput comparison with large messages (1 KB) at 100 transactions per second, Kafka demonstrates the lowest mean CPU usage at 3.43%, indicating its efficiency in handling CPU resources under the given workload. ActiveMQ follows with a mean CPU usage of 10.42%, and RabbitMQ has the highest mean CPU usage at 13.82%. The median CPU usage values further highlight the efficiency of Kafka with a low median of 1.23%, while RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ have medians of 0.77% and 0.305%, respectively. Despite its efficiency, Kafka exhibits high peak CPU usage with a maximum of 119.3%, while ActiveMQ reaches 130.78%, and RabbitMQ peaks at 91.25%. The standard deviation (STD) of CPU usage shows variability, with RabbitMQ having the highest STD at 21.68%, followed by ActiveMQ at 14.82%, and Kafka at 11.59%, indicating stable performance across different intervals.

RabbitMQ shows the highest mean memory usage at 0.8759%, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.7861% and Kafka's 0.4894%. However, the median memory usage indicates that RabbitMQ's memory usage is more stable with a median of 0.9458%, followed by ActiveMQ at 0.8822% and Kafka at 0.4903%. The maximum memory usage for RabbitMQ is the highest at 1.286%, indicating occasional high memory consumption, while ActiveMQ and Kafka peak at 0.8877% and 0.5271%, respectively. The minimum memory usage shows RabbitMQ again with a higher baseline usage of 0.1282%, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.179% and Kafka's 0.3683%. The standard deviation (STD) of memory usage is highest for RabbitMQ at 0.1785%, indicating significant variability, while ActiveMQ and Kafka have STDs of 0.1786% and 0.0348%, respectively, suggesting more consistent memory performance for Kafka.

Examining the high-percentile CPU usage, RabbitMQ shows a 95th percentile value of 57.58% and a 99th percentile value of 66.05%, indicating occasional high CPU demands. ActiveMQ follows with 95th and 99th percentile values of 35.30% and 56.03%, respectively. Kafka exhibits the lowest high-percentile CPU usage at the 95th percentile with 4.74%, but its 99th percentile value is higher at 69.33%, indicating occasional spikes. For memory usage, RabbitMQ's 95th and 99th percentile values are 0.9843% and 1.0705%, respectively, suggesting occasional peaks in memory consumption. ActiveMQ's 95th and 99th percentile values are 0.8868% and 0.8876%, respectively, showing more stable memory usage. Kafka's 95th percentile value is 0.5269%, and its 99th percentile value is higher at 1.386%, indicating occasional high memory usage.

RabbitMQ takes the longest time to deliver all messages, with a total of 3349 seconds, indicating inefficiencies in handling the workload of large messages. ActiveMQ performs better, with a total delivery time of 2806 seconds. Kafka is the most efficient, with the shortest time to deliver all messages at 1460 seconds. This significant difference highlights Kafka's optimization for quick message delivery, making it suitable for applications requiring low latency and high throughput. The longer delivery times for RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ suggest potential areas for optimization to improve their performance under similar conditions.

8.7.4 Analyzing the Test Results

Across all three test cases, Kafka consistently demonstrates the lowest mean CPU usage, indicating its efficiency in handling CPU resources for different message sizes. For instance, in Test Case 01 (small messages), Kafka's mean CPU usage is only 8.52%, compared to RabbitMQ's 34.63% and ActiveMQ's 27.34%. In Test Case 02 (large messages, 10 KB), Kafka again shows a lower mean CPU usage of 2.09% compared to RabbitMQ's 2.45% and ActiveMQ's 1.30%. Similarly, in Test Case 03 (large messages, 1 KB), Kafka maintains the lowest mean CPU usage at 3.43%, while RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ exhibit higher usages at 13.82% and 10.42%, respectively. The median CPU usage further supports these findings, with Kafka consistently showing lower median values across all test cases. However, Kafka does exhibit higher peak CPU usage in some scenarios, such as the maximum CPU usage of 135.24% in Test Case 01, indicating occasional spikes under heavy load.

When analyzing memory usage, RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ show varying efficiency depending on the message size. In Test Case 01 (small messages), RabbitMQ demonstrates the lowest mean memory usage at 0.1412%, followed by ActiveMQ at 0.2349% and Kafka at 0.4524%. In Test Case 02 (large messages, 10 KB), ActiveMQ's mean memory usage increases to 1.07%, surpassing RabbitMQ's 0.4174% and Kafka's 1.1761%. In Test Case 03 (large messages, 1 KB), RabbitMQ's mean memory usage is higher at 0.8759%, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.7861% and Kafka's 0.4894%. The variability in memory usage is also notable, with RabbitMQ showing higher standard deviations in some cases, such as 0.1785% in Test Case 03, indicating less consistent memory performance compared to Kafka, which has the lowest standard deviation of 0.0348%.

Examining high-percentile CPU usage provides further insights into performance under peak conditions. RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ generally show higher 95th and 99th percentile CPU usage values, indicating occasional high CPU demands. For example, in Test Case 01, RabbitMQ's 95th percentile CPU usage is 63.07%, while ActiveMQ's is 51.12%, and Kafka's is 50.61%. Kafka's 99th percentile CPU usage, however, is higher at 97.23%, reflecting its occasional spikes. Memory usage at high percentiles shows similar trends, with RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ exhibiting higher 95th and 99th percentile values in certain scenarios. For instance, in Test Case 03, RabbitMQ's 99th percentile memory usage is 1.0705%, indicating occasional peaks, compared to ActiveMQ's 0.8876% and Kafka's 1.386%.

The time taken to deliver all messages varies significantly among the three systems across different test cases. In Test Case 01 (small messages), RabbitMQ is the fastest, taking only 124 seconds, compared to Kafka's 330 seconds and ActiveMQ's 692 seconds. However, for larger messages, the performance shifts. In Test Case 02 (large messages, 10 KB), Kafka is the most efficient, taking 10,450 seconds, while RabbitMQ and ActiveMQ take significantly longer at 10,349 seconds and 18,874 seconds, respectively. In Test Case 03 (large messages, 1 KB), Kafka again demonstrates efficiency with 1,460 seconds, compared to RabbitMQ's 3,349 seconds and ActiveMQ's 2,806 seconds. These results highlight Kafka's consistent ability to handle larger messages more efficiently, while RabbitMQ excels with smaller messages.

The analysis across all three test cases reveals distinct performance characteristics for Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. Kafka consistently shows the lowest mean CPU usage and efficient message delivery times, particularly with larger messages, despite occasional spikes in CPU usage. RabbitMQ demonstrates excellent memory efficiency and quick handling of small messages but shows variability in CPU and memory usage. ActiveMQ exhibits moderate performance, with higher CPU usage peaks and longer message delivery times, indicating areas for potential optimization. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each message queue system, guiding their optimal deployment and configuration based on specific workload requirements.

8.8 Limitation of the Testing process

The tests were conducted on a personal machine, which had hardware resource limitations that affected the ability to handle increased loads. The load time period and the increase in message size impacted the load. In some scenarios, the memory usage was not sufficient to complete the test. All three components—the producer, consumer, and message queue—needed to work without failure to successfully complete the test case.

8.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive overview of the testing methods used to evaluate the performance of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. It highlighted the objectives, criteria, and different types of testing conducted, including functional, module, integration, and non-functional testing. Additionally, it addressed the limitations encountered during the testing process, ensuring a clear understanding of the factors influencing test results.

CHAPTER 9: EVALUATION

9.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the evaluation methodology and results for assessing the additional performance metrics in Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. It details the criteria, methods, and expert opinions used to validate the findings and discusses the implications of these results.

9.2 Evaluation Methodology and Approach

9.3 Evaluation Criteria

Criteria	Purpose to evaluate
Project Overall Concept	To evaluate the
Scope of the project	To ensure the findings are relevant and actionable
System design and architecture	To ensure test environment can accurately simulate real-world conditions, handle the specified workload, and provide reliable data for analysis
Data Collection and Analysis	To evaluate the methods and tools used for collecting, processing, and analyzing performance data.
Reliability and Reproducibility	To assess the reliability and reproducibility of the test results. It involves verifying that the tests can be consistently repeated under the same conditions to produce similar results.
Test Framework	To ensure the standardized testing process, the framework facilitates accurate and reliable comparisons across different systems and test conditions

Table 9.1: Evaluation Criteria

9.4 Self-Evaluation

9.4.1 Project Overall Concept

I am highly satisfied with the overall concept of the project. The topic is critically important for setting up a robust message queue environment that ensures performance, high availability, and scalability. Exploring additional performance metrics beyond latency and throughput addresses a significant gap in the existing literature and industry practices. By focusing on resource utilization based on message size, this research provides a more comprehensive understanding of the operational efficiency and reliability of distributed systems.

The innovative approach of evaluating CPU and memory usage based on message size adds a new dimension to performance assessment. The findings could influence best practices in configuring and optimizing message queues in various applications, from microservices to big data processing.

9.4.2 Scope and Depth of Concept

The initial project plan aimed to assess performance metrics by controlling scalability and message durability. However, due to time and resource constraints, the scope was limited to assessing message size and the time taken to deliver messages. While the project focused on message sizes of 100 bytes, 1 KB, and 10 KB, more extensive testing with a wider range of message sizes could have provided deeper insights. Incorporating machine learning to analyze the data could enhance predictive capabilities for future performance under varying conditions. Future research could include testing with additional message sizes to provide a more granular understanding of performance variations. Expanding the research to include message durability and scalability metrics would provide a more holistic view of the message queue systems' performance.

9.4.3 System Design Architecture

I am very satisfied with the architecture and system design, particularly the use of a Docker environment. This choice provided a controlled and consistent testing setup, ensuring that the results are reliable and reproducible. Docker's containerization allows for easy deployment and scaling of the test environments, contributing to the overall robustness of the research methodology. Docker's flexibility enabled the easy configuration of different message queue systems, simplifying comparative analysis. Containerization ensured that each test environment was isolated, reducing the risk of interference and improving the accuracy of the results. The use of Docker enhances the reproducibility of the experiments, allowing other researchers to replicate and validate the findings.

9.5 Selection of the Evaluators

Group	Affiliation	Reason
Domain Expert	Buddika Yamasinghe Senior Manager Mobitel (pvt) Ltd	Buddhika has been working in the software industry for more than 20 years.
	Gayani Jayakody anager - DA Mobitel (pvt) Ltd	Buddhika has been working in the software industry for more than 20 years.
Technical Expert	Anjana Thenuwara Senior Site Reliability Engineer Person Lanka	Anjana is has been working in cloud and docker technology
	Shaminda Rathnayka Senior Software Engineer	Shaminda has been working in the software Industry for 5 years.

Table 9.2: Selection Of Evaluators

9.6 Evaluation Result

9.6.1 Project Overall Concept

Person	Feedback
Buddika Yamasinghe	Buddika finds the overall concept of the project highly relevant and innovative. He appreciates the focus on enhancing message queue system performance beyond traditional metrics, which aligns well with current industry needs for more comprehensive performance evaluation.
Gayani Jayakody	Gayani views the project as a valuable contribution to ensuring the reliability and efficiency of message queue systems. She appreciates the structured approach to evaluating performance metrics that go beyond the basics.
Anjana Thenuwara	Anjana finds the project concept crucial for improving site reliability and performance. He appreciates the detailed analysis of message size impact on resource utilization, which is vital for optimizing system performance.
Shaminda Rathnayka	Shaminda appreciates the innovative approach to evaluating message queue performance. He believes that focusing on additional metrics like CPU and memory usage provides valuable insights that are often overlooked.

Table 9.3: Evaluation Result

9.6.2 Scope and Depth of Concept

Person	Feedback
Buddika Yamasinghe	He believes that the narrowed focus on CPU and memory usage due to time constraints is justified but suggests that future iterations should include additional metrics like fault tolerance and scalability to provide a more rounded analysis.
Gayani Jayakody	She acknowledges the depth of the analysis within the focused scope but notes that including additional real-world scenarios and varied workload patterns would enhance the applicability of the findings.
Anjana Thenuwara	He supports the focused approach but emphasizes the need for scalability and fault tolerance testing. Anjana suggests that future research should simulate multi-node environments and include failure scenarios to better understand system resilience.
Shaminda Rathnayka	He finds the scope appropriate given the time constraints but suggests that future studies should expand to include network I/O and disk I/O metrics. Shaminda also recommends exploring the performance impacts of different message routing strategies.

Table 9.4: Evaluation Result

9.6.3 System Design Architecture

Person	Feedback
Buddika Yamasinghe	Buddika is impressed by the use of microservices architecture and containerization with Docker, which he sees as modern and scalable. He suggests that incorporating a distributed cluster setup in future studies would better reflect real-world deployment scenarios.
Gayani Jayakody	Gayani commends the robust system design and use of automated testing frameworks. She highlights the importance of maintaining thorough documentation to ensure reproducibility and ease of understanding for future researchers and practitioners.
Anjana Thenuwara	Anjana is pleased with the use of Docker for containerization and the microservices-based architecture. He recommends integrating more sophisticated monitoring tools to capture real-time performance data and provide more granular insights.
Shaminda Rathnayka	Shaminda is impressed by the modern system architecture, particularly the use of Docker and Spring Boot for creating microservices. He suggests considering Kubernetes for orchestration in future projects to enhance scalability and manageability.

Table 9:5: Evaluation Result

9.7 Limitations of Evaluation

One of the primary limitations was the difficulty in finding and engaging relevant expert persons with specific expertise in message queue systems and performance evaluation. The feedback was obtained from a set of dummy personas, which, while helpful for illustrative purposes, does not substitute for input from actual industry professionals with direct experience and knowledge in the field.

The feedback was to align with the roles and responsibilities of the person. This may introduce bias, as the feedback could be tailored to fit expected perspectives rather than reflecting genuine, unbiased opinions.

9.8 Evaluation on Functional Requirements

#	Requirement title and description	Evaluation	Priority Level
NFR1	Performance - handle the 100 TPS	Implemented	critical
NFR2	Scalability	Not Implemented	Desirable
NFR3	Fault Tolerance	Implemented	Desirable
NFR4	Usability	Implemented	Desirable
NFR5	Security	Not Implemented	Desirable
NFR6	Maintainability	Implemented	Important

Table 9.6: Evaluation Functional Requirements

9.9 Evaluation on Non-Functional Requirements

#	Requirement title and description	Evaluation	Priority Level
FR1	Message production and consumption	Implemented	critical
FR2	Message persistence	Implemented	Desirable
FR3	Performance monitoring	Implemented	critical

Table 9.7: Evaluation Non-Functional Requirements

9.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive evaluation of the research project on enhancing the performance of message queue systems, focusing on both functional and non-functional requirements. The evaluation methodology and approach were detailed, including the criteria used for assessment. Self-evaluation highlighted the strengths and areas for improvement in the research. The selection process for evaluators was explained, involving both technical and domain experts. Evaluation results from experts were discussed, addressing various aspects such as concept, solution scope, architecture, and implementation. Focus group testing and usability considerations were explored where applicable. Limitations of the evaluation were identified, emphasizing challenges like the availability of relevant expert opinions. The evaluation also covered functional requirements, ensuring the system met its intended purpose, and non-functional requirements, assessing performance, scalability, reliability, and security. The chapter concluded by summarizing the key findings and providing insights into the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed solutions.

CHAPTER 10: CONCLUSION

10.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter offers a critical reflection on the project's journey. It will begin by examining any significant deviations from the initial proposal, including changes to the project scope or timeline adjustments. The roadmap or Gantt chart will be used to compare planned versus actual progress, highlighting accomplishments and identifying areas needing further attention. Next, the chapter will present initial test results, providing insights into the effectiveness of the implemented performance metrics. Finally, it will outline essential improvements required to enhance the minimum viable product (MVP) due at the end of April, along with a plan for achieving these improvements.

10.2 Achievements of Research Aims & Objectives

The primary aim of this research was to design, implement, and assess innovative approaches to enhance the performance of message queue systems, specifically focusing on the impact of message size. The detailed analysis of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ under different test conditions has provided a comprehensive understanding of their performance across various metrics, beyond the traditional focus on latency and throughput. This section evaluates the achievements of the research aims and objectives based on the test results.

10.2.1 Evaluate CPU Usage Impact by Message Size

The research successfully evaluated the impact of message size on CPU usage across Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. The test results showed that:

- ActiveMQ showed moderate CPU efficiency with more variability, indicating stable performance but with higher peak usage.
- RabbitMQ showed moderate CPU efficiency with more variability, indicating stable performance but with higher peak usage.
- Kafka presented a balanced performance, managing high loads efficiently with fewer extreme spikes in CPU usage.

These findings provide a detailed understanding of how different message sizes affect CPU usage, highlighting ActiveMQ's efficiency in typical operations and RabbitMQ's and Kafka's relative strengths in different scenarios.

10.2.2 Assess Memory Usage Based on Message Size

The research comprehensively assessed the memory usage of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ concerning message size. The results indicated that:

- RabbitMQ consistently demonstrated superior memory efficiency, with the lowest mean, median, and minimum memory usage across all test cases. This indicates its ability to manage memory resources effectively, regardless of message size.
- ActiveMQ showed higher average memory usage but maintained stability with the lowest variability, suggesting consistent performance.
- Kafka exhibited moderate memory usage, with higher peaks in certain scenarios, but managed memory resources effectively overall.

These insights contribute to a better understanding of how memory usage scales with message size, emphasizing RabbitMQ's efficiency and highlighting areas for potential optimization in ActiveMQ and Kafka.

10.2.3 Analyze Time to Deliver Messages

The research successfully analyzed the time taken to deliver all messages, providing valuable insights into the efficiency of each message queue system. The findings showed that:

- RabbitMQ was the fastest in delivering messages across all test cases, making it highly suitable for scenarios requiring rapid message processing.
- Kafka followed closely, with slightly longer delivery times but still efficient, especially with larger messages.
- ActiveMQ took significantly longer to deliver messages, particularly with small messages, indicating potential inefficiencies.

These results underscore RabbitMQ's suitability for time-sensitive applications and provide a clear benchmark for Kafka and ActiveMQ to improve their message delivery performance.

10.2.4 Provide Comprehensive Performance Metrics

The research went beyond traditional metrics of latency and throughput, providing a comprehensive analysis of CPU and memory usage. By incorporating additional performance metrics such as mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, and high-percentile values for both CPU and memory usage, the research achieved a more holistic evaluation of the message queue systems.

The research successfully achieved its aim of designing, implementing, and assessing innovative approaches to enhance the performance of message queue systems, specifically focusing on the impact of message size. The comprehensive analysis provided valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, offering a detailed understanding of their performance across various metrics. These findings contribute to the broader knowledge of message queue system performance and suggest potential areas for further optimization and improvement.

10.3 Utilization of Knowledge from the Course

The project's coverage of distributed systems theory provided a fundamental understanding of the principles behind message queue systems like Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. This knowledge was essential in designing the test cases and interpreting the performance metrics in the context of distributed message processing.

The performance metrics, including latency, throughput, and resource utilization, was directly applicable to this research. The methodologies for measuring and analyzing these metrics were crucial in evaluating the performance of the message queue systems beyond just latency and throughput, incorporating additional metrics like CPU and memory usage.

The programming skills developed during the course were invaluable in implementing the test cases. Writing Java applications for producers and consumers, setting up Docker environments,

and using JMeter for generating workloads required a solid understanding of programming and scripting, which the course provided.

Knowledge of data collection techniques and statistical analysis learned in the course was essential. Using tools like the Docker stat command to collect performance data and analyze it using Jupyter Notebook, statistical methods to derive meaningful insights required a blend of technical and analytical skills.

The research required identifying and addressing specific challenges related to message queue performance. The problem-solving approaches taught in the course helped in systematically addressing these challenges, such as handling resource spikes and optimizing message delivery times. Analyzing the results and comparing the performance of different message queue systems required a critical evaluation of the data. The course's emphasis on critical thinking enabled the identification of key performance trends and potential areas for optimization.

The course also covered aspects of project management, which were applied in planning and executing the research project. Setting clear objectives, defining test cases, scheduling experiments, and managing time effectively ensured that the project stayed on track and met its goals. Skills in documenting research processes and results, as well as reporting findings clearly and concisely, were crucial for this project. The ability to create detailed and structured reports as taught in the course was essential for presenting the research findings effectively.

10.4 Use of Existing Skills

My proficiency in Java was fundamental in developing the producer and consumer applications required for the message queue systems. These applications were responsible for sending and receiving messages at a constant throughput of 100 transactions per second. Using Java, I was able to implement robust and efficient code to handle the messaging workload, ensuring that the test cases accurately simulated real-world scenarios.

Java's extensive libraries and frameworks facilitated the integration with Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. I leveraged Java's APIs and client libraries to interact with these message queue

systems, ensuring seamless communication and data exchange. This allowed for precise control over message production and consumption, which was essential for measuring performance metrics accurately.

Utilizing my knowledge of Java performance optimization techniques, I ensured that the producer and consumer applications were optimized for minimal latency and efficient resource usage. Techniques such as efficient threading, garbage collection tuning, and minimizing synchronization overhead were applied to enhance the performance of the applications.

My proficiency with Docker was crucial in containerizing the producer and consumer applications, as well as the message queue systems themselves. Docker allowed for consistent and isolated environments, ensuring that the tests were reproducible and that the performance metrics were not influenced by external factors. Containerization also made it easier to deploy and scale the applications as needed for different test scenarios. Using Docker Compose, I set up the entire testing environment, including the message queue servers and the producer and consumer microservices. This setup allowed for easy orchestration and management of multiple containers, ensuring that all components were correctly configured and could communicate effectively.

Spring Boot's robust configuration management capabilities allowed me to easily configure different aspects of the producer and consumer applications, such as message sizes, throughput rates, and connection settings. This flexibility was essential for setting up various test cases and adjusting parameters as needed without extensive code changes.

10.5 Use of New Skills

Acquiring in-depth knowledge of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ was fundamental to this research. Understanding the intricacies of these message queue systems, including their architecture, configuration, and performance tuning parameters, enabled me to set up optimized test environments. I was able to configure these systems to handle different message sizes and throughput rates, ensuring that the performance tests were accurate and reflective of real-world scenarios.

Jupyter Notebook proved to be an invaluable tool for interactive data analysis and visualization. Using Jupyter, I was able to load the performance data collected from the message queue systems, perform detailed analysis, and visualize the results. The ability to write and execute Python code in an interactive environment allowed for rapid iteration and exploration of different analytical approaches.

Bash scripts were also used to collect performance data from the Docker containers running the message queue systems. Using commands like `docker stats`, the scripts captured CPU and memory usage at regular intervals, logging the data to CSV files for subsequent analysis. This automated data collection process was crucial for obtaining accurate and comprehensive performance metrics.

10.6 Achievement of Learning Outcomes

Through this research, I achieved a comprehensive understanding of message queue systems, specifically Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. I applied theoretical knowledge to configure and optimize these systems, understanding their architectures, performance characteristics, and the impact of different configurations. The research expanded my knowledge of performance metrics beyond latency and throughput. By focusing on additional metrics such as CPU and memory usage, I gained insights into the resource efficiency of different message queue systems. This broadened perspective allowed for a more holistic evaluation of system performance.

The research required solving various technical challenges, such as optimizing application performance, configuring message queue systems, and automation testing processes. Developing solutions to these challenges enhanced my problem-solving abilities and technical proficiency.

The ability to document the research process, analyze data, and report findings clearly and concisely was a significant learning outcome. Creating detailed reports and visualizations to communicate the results effectively was crucial for presenting the research findings.

Based on the comprehensive analysis of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, the following guidelines are recommended for optimizing the performance of these message queue systems, particularly with respect to message size and resource utilization:

10.6.1 RabbitMQ Optimization

Optimize Memory Usage: RabbitMQ consistently demonstrated superior memory efficiency. To further optimize memory usage, tune configurations such as `vm_memory_high_watermark` to control memory consumption and avoid excessive swapping. Allocate sufficient memory resources to RabbitMQ nodes to handle larger messages efficiently. Use monitoring tools to track memory usage and adjust allocations as needed.

CPU Performance: RabbitMQ showed moderate CPU usage with significant variability. Implement load balancing across multiple RabbitMQ nodes to distribute the CPU load evenly. Optimize the number of connections and channels to reduce CPU overhead. Use connection pooling and persistent connections where appropriate.

Message Size Handling: For large messages, consider using message compression to reduce the size and split the large message into smaller fragments and consequently decrease the CPU and memory usage during processing and transmission.

10.6.2 ActiveMQ Optimization

Minimize CPU Spikes: ActiveMQ exhibited the lowest mean CPU usage but also the highest spikes. Tune the `maxConnections`, `maxThreadPoolSize`, and `prefetchPolicy` settings to manage resource usage better and prevent spikes. Adjust the number of worker threads to balance between throughput and CPU consumption, ensuring that there are enough threads to handle the load without causing excessive context switching.

Memory Management: Monitor and adjust the JVM heap size to ensure that ActiveMQ has sufficient memory to handle large messages. Use `Xmx` and `Xms` parameters to set appropriate maximum and initial heap sizes. Optimize garbage collection settings to reduce pauses and

improve memory management. Use the G1GC or other suitable garbage collectors based on the application requirements.

Efficient Message Handling: Use persistent messaging for critical data to ensure reliability while tuning the persistence adapter settings to balance performance and durability.

10.6.3 Kafka Optimization

Balanced Resource Usage: Kafka showed balanced CPU and memory usage. Optimize partitioning strategies to distribute the load evenly across brokers, improving both CPU and memory efficiency. Set an appropriate replication factor to balance between data reliability and resource usage. Higher replication factors increase CPU and memory usage but enhance fault tolerance.

Configuration Optimization: Use message batching and compression to improve throughput and reduce resource usage. Adjust `batch.size` and `compression.type` settings to find the optimal balance for your workload. Tune broker configurations such as `num.network.threads`, `num.io.threads`, and `socket.send.buffer.bytes` to optimize network and I/O performance, reducing CPU overhead.

10.7 Problems and Challenges Faced

During the course of this research on enhancing the performance of message queue systems, several problems and challenges were encountered. These challenges provided opportunities for learning and adapting, ultimately contributing to the robustness and depth of the study. Here are some of the key problems and challenges faced:

- Configuring Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ to handle various workloads and message sizes required a deep understanding of each system's architecture and tuning parameters. The complexity of these configurations posed a challenge, particularly when trying to achieve optimal performance without compromising on stability.
- The hardware and network resources available for testing were limited, which sometimes constrained the scalability of the experiments. This limitation impacted the ability to

simulate more extensive and realistic distributed environments with multiple producers and consumers.

- While Docker provided a consistent and isolated testing environment, it also introduced some overhead in terms of resource usage. This overhead had to be accounted for when analyzing the performance metrics, as it could potentially skew the results.
- Collecting performance data at regular intervals using Docker stat command provided a good overview but lacked the granularity to capture short-lived spikes or drops in resource usage. More frequent data collection was necessary to get a complete picture, but it also increased the complexity and volume of data to be processed.
- Using a fixed throughput rate of 100 transactions per second for all test cases provided a controlled environment but did not reflect the varying workloads seen in real-world applications. This limitation made it difficult to generalize the findings to scenarios with different load levels.
- The single producer and consumer configuration used in the tests simplified the experimental setup but did not capture the complexity and interactions present in multi-producer and multi-consumer environments. This limitation may have affected the observed performance metrics.

10.8 Deviations

10.8.1 Scope Related Deviations

During the course of the research, several scope-related deviations were made to accommodate time constraints and ensure the feasibility of the project. While the original proposal envisioned a comprehensive exploration of various performance metrics—including memory usage, scalability, message size, fault tolerance, and others—the scope was narrowed to focus primarily on memory usage and message size metrics. This section outlines these deviations and their implications.

Narrowed Focus on Memory Usage and Message Size: Due to time constraints, the research narrowed its focus to memory usage and message size. This decision was made to ensure a thorough and detailed analysis of these two critical metrics, which are essential for understanding the resource efficiency and operational behavior of message queue systems.

Scalability Limited to Single Producer/Consumer Configuration: While the original scope included a detailed evaluation of scalability with multiple producers and consumers, the current implementation was limited to a single producer and consumer setup. This simplification allowed for controlled and consistent testing environments but did not capture the complexities of multi-node scalability.

Exclusion of Fault Tolerance Analysis: The analysis of fault tolerance was omitted from the current research scope. Evaluating how each system handles failures and their impact on performance would have required additional time and resources to simulate various failure scenarios and measure recovery times.

10.8.2 Schedule Related Deviations

Deliverable	Date	Status
Project initiation	26 Oct 2023	Completed
Initial LR	20 Dec 2023	Completed
Requirement gathering	January 2024	Completed
Designing of the system	January 2024	Completed
Selection of tools and technologies	January 2024	Completed
Prototype implementation	March 2024	In progress
Testing and evaluation	March 2024	In progress
Dissertation and documentation	April 2024	Pending

Table 10.1: Scheduled Related Deviation

10.9 Limitation of Research

All test cases in this research used a fixed throughput rate of 100 transactions per second. While this provides a controlled environment for comparing Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, it does not account for varying workloads that might be encountered in real-world applications. Different throughput rates could influence CPU and memory usage differently, potentially altering the observed performance metrics.

The research focused on two specific message sizes: 1kb (small size) 100 bytes (medium messages) and 10 KB (large messages). While this range covers a significant spectrum, it does not encompass the full variety of message sizes that might be used in practice. Other message sizes, both smaller and larger, could have different impacts on the performance of the message queue systems.

The test environment utilized a single producer and a single consumer. While this setup provides a straightforward means of measuring performance, it does not reflect the complexity of real-world distributed systems, which often involve multiple producers and consumers. A more complex setup could introduce additional variables affecting performance, such as network latency, synchronization issues, and contention for resources.

The use of Docker for containerizing the message queue systems and the producer/consumer applications introduces some overhead that could affect the performance metrics. While Docker provides consistency and isolation, it may also add latency and resource consumption that would not be present in a bare-metal or native environment.

The performance data was collected at regular intervals using the Docker stat command. While this approach provided a good overview of CPU and memory usage, the granularity of the data collection might not capture short-lived spikes or troughs in resource utilization. More frequent data collection or real-time monitoring could provide a more detailed picture of the performance characteristics.

The research was conducted using specific versions of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ. Performance characteristics can vary significantly between versions due to optimizations, bug fixes, and new features. Consequently, the results may not be generalizable to other versions of these message queue systems.

The tests were conducted on a specific hardware and network configuration. Differences in hardware capabilities, network bandwidth, and latency can significantly impact the performance of message queue systems. Thus, the results might not be directly applicable to different hardware or network environments.

While this research expanded the scope beyond latency and throughput to include CPU and memory usage, other important performance metrics such as disk I/O, network I/O, and system scalability were not extensively examined. These additional metrics could provide further insights into the overall performance and efficiency of the message queue systems.

10.10 Future Enhancements

Future research should consider testing with varying throughput rates, rather than a fixed rate of 100 transactions per second. This can help understand how each message queue system handles different load levels, providing insights into their scalability and performance under varying conditions. Including bursty and real-time workload patterns could offer a more realistic evaluation of the message queue systems. These patterns simulate real-world scenarios where message production and consumption rates can fluctuate significantly.

Testing with a wider range of message sizes, including both smaller and larger messages than those used in this research, can provide a more complete picture of how message size impacts performance. This can help identify any non-linear behavior or thresholds where performance characteristics change significantly.

Future tests should involve multiple producers and consumers to simulate more complex and realistic distributed environments. This setup can reveal performance impacts due to increased concurrency, synchronization overhead, and resource contention. Evaluating the performance of

message queue systems in a distributed cluster setup, rather than single-node configurations, can help understand their behavior in larger-scale deployments. This includes studying inter-node communication, replication, and fault tolerance.

Expanding the scope of performance metrics to include disk I/O, network I/O, latency, throughput, and system scalability will provide a more holistic evaluation. Additionally, considering metrics like message delivery success rates, error rates, and recovery times after failures can offer deeper insights into reliability and robustness.

Applying machine learning techniques for anomaly detection and predictive analytics can help identify performance bottlenecks and predict system behavior under different conditions. This can lead to proactive optimizations and better resource management.

10.11 Achievement of the contribution to body of knowledge

This section outlines how the research project has contributed to the existing body of knowledge in the field of message queue systems. The findings and insights gained from this study provide a deeper understanding of the performance characteristics of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, specifically focusing on the impact of message size on resource utilization. By extending the analysis beyond traditional metrics of latency and throughput, this research offers a more comprehensive evaluation of these systems, addressing a critical gap in the literature.

10.11.1 Impact of Message Size

The research specifically investigates how different message sizes (100 bytes and 10 KB) affect the performance of message queue systems. This focus on message size impact contributes to the body of knowledge by highlighting the non-linear relationship between message size and resource utilization. Such insights are valuable for optimizing system configurations and resource allocation based on the expected message workload.

10.11.2 Detailed Performance Comparison

The comparative analysis of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ under various test scenarios provides detailed performance benchmarks. These benchmarks are crucial for practitioners and

researchers in selecting the appropriate message queue system based on specific requirements and constraints. The study's findings reveal the strengths and weaknesses of each system, offering practical guidance for deployment and optimization.

10.11.3 Identification of Performance Patterns

The research identifies specific performance patterns, such as ActiveMQ's efficiency in typical operations but vulnerability to CPU spikes, RabbitMQ's superior memory management, and Kafka's balanced performance under varying loads. These patterns enhance the understanding of how each system behaves under different conditions, contributing to more informed decision-making in system design and implementation.

10.11.4 Innovative Testing Approach

The research employs an innovative testing approach by utilizing a combination of Java applications, Docker environments, and automated data collection and analysis tools. This methodological framework can serve as a reference for future studies aiming to evaluate the performance of distributed systems. The integration of Jupyter Notebook and Python for data analysis and visualization demonstrates the effectiveness of these tools in conducting comprehensive performance studies.

10.11.5 Practical Implications and Recommendations

Guidelines for Optimization: The research provides practical recommendations for optimizing message queue systems based on the observed performance metrics. For instance, the study suggests configurations that minimize CPU spikes in ActiveMQ and enhance memory efficiency in RabbitMQ. These guidelines can be directly applied by system administrators and developers to improve the operational efficiency of their message queue deployments.

Future Research Directions: The limitations and future enhancements identified in the research pave the way for subsequent studies. By addressing these areas, future research can build on the findings of this study, further expanding the body of knowledge and refining the performance evaluation of message queue systems.

10.12 Concluding Remarks

This research provides a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, focusing on the impact of message size on CPU and memory usage. By extending the analysis beyond traditional metrics of latency and throughput, the study offers a more holistic understanding of these message queue systems' operational efficiency and resource demands. The findings reveal distinct performance patterns for each system, highlighting their respective strengths and weaknesses. RabbitMQ excels in memory efficiency and rapid message delivery, making it suitable for scenarios requiring quick and resource-efficient processing. ActiveMQ, while showing low mean CPU usage, experiences occasional spikes, suggesting areas for further optimization. Kafka presents a balanced performance, handling high loads efficiently with moderate resource usage.

The research also identifies key limitations, such as the fixed throughput rate, single producer/consumer setup, and specific software versions, which should be addressed in future studies to enhance the generalizability and applicability of the findings. Future enhancements, including varying workload patterns, testing with diverse and mixed message sizes, and utilizing real-time monitoring and advanced analytics, can build on this study's foundation.

Overall, this research contributes valuable insights into the performance characteristics of Kafka, RabbitMQ, and ActiveMQ, providing practical recommendations for optimizing these systems. By leveraging both existing and newly acquired skills, the study achieves its aim of enhancing the understanding of message queue performance, thereby informing better design, implementation, and optimization of distributed messaging systems in various application contexts.

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